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Vector control for malaria prevention during humanitarian emergencies: a systematic review and meta-analysis

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Summary (max 300 words)

Background

Humanitarian emergencies are equivalent to major disasters, which can lead to population displacement, food insecurity, severe health system disruptions and malaria epidemics among immunologically-naïve individuals. We conducted a systematic review and meta-analysis of the impact of different vector control interventions on malaria disease burden during humanitarian emergencies.

Methods

We searched 10 electronic databases, 2 clinical trials registries and grey literature from 59 stakeholders, with no restrictions on language, date, or study design. Studies were eligible if the population was affected by a humanitarian emergency in a malaria endemic region, any vector control intervention was evaluated, and malaria infection risk measured. We did random-effects meta-analyses to calculate pooled risk ratios for randomised controlled trials, odds ratios for dichotomous outcomes and incidence rate ratios for clinical malaria in non-randomised studies, respectively. Certainty of evidence was evaluated using the Grading of Recommendations Assessment, Development and Evaluation (GRADE) approach. This study is registered with PROSPERO: CRD42020214961.

Findings

Of 12,475 studies screened, 22 studies were eligible for inclusion. All studies were conducted between 1989 and 2018 in chronic emergencies, with 616,611 participants

from 9 countries, evaluating seven different interventions. Insecticide-treated nets significantly decreased *P. falciparum* and *P. vivax* incidence (RR 0.55 [95% CI: 0.37-0.79] and RR 0.69 [95% CI: 0.51-0.94], respectively; high certainty). Evidence for an effect of Indoor residual spraying on *P. falciparum* and *P. vivax* incidence was of very low certainty (rate ratio 0.57 [95% CI: 0.53-0.61] and rate ratio 0.51 [95% CI: 0.49-0.52], respectively). Topical repellents were associated with reductions in malaria infection (RR 0.58 [95% CI: 0.35-0.97]; moderate certainty). Moderate to high certainty evidence for an effect of insecticide-treated *chaddars* (equivalent to shawls) and insecticide-treated cattle on malaria outcomes was evident in some emergency settings. There was very low certainty evidence on the effect of insecticide-treated clothing.

Interpretation

Study findings strengthen and support World Health Organization policy recommendations to deploy ITNs during humanitarian emergencies. There is an urgent need to evaluate and adopt novel interventions for integrated malaria vector control during humanitarian emergencies.

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Research in context

Evidence before this study

Humanitarian emergencies are a singular event or series of events which critically threaten the health, safety, security and well-being of a community or other large population. Irrespective of whether the source of the humanitarian emergency is natural, climate-related (e.g. earthquakes, tsunamis, floods, drought, cyclones or volcanic eruptions) or man-made (e.g. armed conflicts, war or acts of terrorism), these crises may be accompanied by increased risk of malaria epidemics and incidence of severe disease. Reasons for this may include; mass-displacement causing immunologically-naïve individuals to move into high malaria transmission areas or vice-versa, and increased vector-breeding due to flooding, loss of infrastructure and inappropriate waste drainage/management systems. Insufficient access to diagnosis and treatment services and the presence of co-morbidities, such as malnutrition and other infectious diseases, further exacerbate the problem, resulting in increased levels of malaria morbidity and mortality in these settings.

When reviewed previously by the World Health Organization (WHO), the evidence for vector control tools deployed during humanitarian emergencies was considered weak, with limited recommendations given based on proven intervention efficacy during non-emergency situations.

Between 15 October 2020 and 02 November 2020, we searched Cochrane Infectious Disease Group Specialized Register, Central Register of Controlled Trials (CENTRAL), MEDLINE (OvidSP), Africa-Wide Information (EBSCO), the WHO Global Index Medicus, the Science Citation Index Expanded (Web of Science), the Conference Proceedings Citation Index – Science (Web of Science), Embase (OvidSP), Global Health (CABI), and LILACS, without restriction on language, date or study design, to identify studies where vector control interventions were evaluated during a humanitarian emergency and their impact on malaria infection assessed. Furthermore, we also searched ClinicalTrials.gov and the ISRCTN registry to identify ongoing trials and retrieved relevant grey literature from 29 key non-governmental organizations (NGOs), 24 donors, stakeholders and policy makers and 6 industrial partners. Depending on the database, a combination of ~200 different search terms were used for literature retrieval. After assessing all outcomes using GRADE methodology, the certainty of the evidence ranged from low to high.

Added value of this study

In this systematic review and meta-analysis, we investigated of the impact of different vector control interventions on malaria disease burden during humanitarian emergencies to provide a comprehensive global evidence summary and highlight the complexities associated with generating robust evidence for vector control tools in such settings. Insecticide-treated nets (ITNs) were confirmed as effective at preventing both *Plasmodium falciparum* and *P. vivax* malaria infection. Other experimental vector control tools, insecticide-treated *chaddars* and insecticide treatment of cattle, also showed promise in individual studies. However, key differences in vector species behaviours may influence the efficacy of these interventions between emergency settings and additional randomised studies are warranted.

Implications of all the available evidence

Currently, no formal guidelines exist for malaria vector control in humanitarian emergencies. The results of this systematic review and meta-analysis support the use of ITNs in these settings. Multiple barriers affecting the evaluation of vector control tools in humanitarian emergencies were identified, including their rapid onset, ethical design of appropriate control groups, inequitable access of study participants to concomitant improvements in malaria diagnosis and treatment, heterogeneities in refugee camp infrastructure and policy restrictions imposed by recent revisions of the evidence criteria for vector control tools, requiring two randomised controlled trials with epidemiological endpoints. Most importantly there is a clear and urgent need to evaluate novel, innovative, emergency-specific vector control tools to complement ITN distributions and IRS campaigns and parallel strategies to improve policy evaluation processes and market access to stimulate the development of these 'niche' vector control tools . Study findings have contributed directly to the latest WHO guidelines for malaria vector control.

Introduction (3500 words main text)

Humanitarian emergencies, of either natural or anthropogenic origins, are equivalent to major disasters, which can lead to large-scale population movement, food insecurity and severe health system disruptions. As of late-2021, the United Nations Refugee Agency estimates there are 82.4 million forcibly displaced people worldwide, including 48 million internally displaced people (IDPs), 26.4 million refugees, 4.1 million asylum-seekers and 3.9 million Venezuelans displaced abroad¹. Almost two-thirds of persons affected by humanitarian emergencies inhabit malaria endemic areas², particularly the World Health Organization (WHO) African region, which currently accounts for 94% of both malaria cases and deaths globally³. Mass displacement can increase the risk of malaria epidemics and incidence of severe disease, especially when populations with little to no prior malaria exposure move into areas of more intense transmission or when individuals with subclinical infections transit into urban settings. Both scenarios render these populations vulnerable to malaria due to lack of protective immunity, which is further exacerbated by increased population density and breakdown of infrastructures. Inadequate water, sanitation, and hygiene (WASH) facilities, drainage and waste management systems all contribute to high levels of vector breeding and increased malaria transmission. Limited and overburdened national malaria control programmes and health services result in insufficient access to treatment and control measures, with poor health outcomes worsened by concomitant infectious diseases, malnutrition and anaemia⁴.

During the initial phase of a humanitarian emergency, typically characterized by elevated mortality rates, poor access to effective healthcare for the affected population and response needs that are beyond local or national capacity, the first priorities for malaria control are prompt and effective diagnosis and treatment⁴. Selection of complementary vector control interventions in these situations depends on levels of malaria infection risk, human population behaviour (mobility, sleeping location and vector exposure), local vector population behaviour (indoor biting, early evening or night biting) and type of shelter available (*ad-hoc* refuse materials, plastic sheeting, tents or more permanent housing)⁵. In some emergencies, effective case management can be supplemented with distribution of insecticide-treated nets (ITNs) first targeting the most vulnerable populations such as pregnant women and children under-5 years old, with the goal of achieving and maintaining universal coverage⁶⁻⁸. Indoor residual spraying (IRS) can be applied in well-organised, camp settings, such as transit camps, but is generally not feasible when dwellings are scattered widely, of a temporary nature, or constructed with surfaces that are unsuitable for spraying⁹. IRS is more appropriate for protecting larger populations where housing is permanent and structurally sound, as more often established when emergencies progress into the post-acute/recovery phases⁴.

Other innovative community-level and personal vector control interventions have been designed specifically for humanitarian emergencies, including insecticide-treated-shelter materials (plastic sheeting, tarpaulins and tents¹⁰⁻¹²), bed sheets¹³⁻¹⁵, blankets¹⁶, clothing¹⁷, hammocks¹⁸ and wall lining^{19,20}; as well as the use of topical insecticides for individual use^{21,22} or to treat community livestock²³. However, to date the evidence basis for the effectiveness of vector control tools deployed during humanitarian emergencies has been considered weak by the WHO and there have been insufficient systematic analyses to develop policy recommendations for interventions other than ITNs and IRS; recommendations for these are based on their proven efficacy in non-emergency situations⁵. To address this deficit and with a view to highlight the complexities associated with generating robust evidence for vector control tools in these settings, we did a systematic review and meta-analysis of the impact of different vector control interventions on malaria disease burden during humanitarian emergencies.

Methods

Search strategy and selection criteria

This systematic review and meta-analysis adhered to the updated PRISMA 2020 guidelines^{24,25} (Appendix: supplementary table 1). We searched Cochrane Infectious Disease Group Specialized Register, Central Register of Controlled Trials (CENTRAL), MEDLINE (OvidSP), Africa-Wide Information (EBSCO), the WHO Global Index Medicus, the Science Citation Index Expanded (Web of Science), the Conference Proceedings Citation Index – Science (Web of Science), Embase (OvidSP), Global Health (CABI), and LILACS to identify relevant studies. We did not impose any language, date or study design restrictions. Bibliographies of relevant articles retrieved from the searches were checked for additional publications. We also searched ClinicalTrials.gov (www.clinicaltrials.gov) and the ISRCTN registry (www.isrctn.com) to identify ongoing trials. Grey literature from 29 key non-governmental organizations (NGOs), 24 donors, stakeholders and policy makers and 6 industrial partners were also searched. A full description of the search methodology and terms is available from: https://osf.io/r6n7k/?view_only=38d7a705d743435097f170bbebaa0623. Five reviewers (LAM, JFA, BP, LP and KC) used predetermined eligibility criteria to screen records and full texts, with adjudication by consensus in cases of disagreement. We ensured that multiple publications of the same study were included once. We listed excluded studies, together with their reasons for exclusion, in a 'Characteristics of Excluded Studies' table (Appendix: supplementary table 2). The study selection process is illustrated in a PRISMA diagram (Figure 1). References were managed using EndNote X9.3.3 and screened using Rayyan²⁶.

Studies retrieved were eligible for inclusion in the systematic review and meta-analysis if they satisfied all criteria: the study population consisted of individuals of either all age groups, or children of specified age groups (i.e. <5 years, >5-15 years), affected by humanitarian emergencies (any phase) in malaria endemic regions; any malaria-specific vector control intervention was evaluated; and the primary outcome of interest was malaria infection risk, measured as case incidence, infection incidence or parasite prevalence. Studies retrieved were eligible for inclusion in secondary analyses, where none of the primary malaria risk indicators were measured, but at least one of the following secondary outcomes were reported: all-cause mortality, severe malaria, anaemia prevalence (<10g/dL), entomological inoculation rate (EIR), adult mosquito density, sporozoite rate, intervention durability, occurrence of adverse events and user acceptability/usage. The following study designs were eligible for inclusion: Cluster-randomised, controlled before-and-after, cross-sectional, non-randomized cross-over, case-control and cohort studies, case series, interrupted time series and programmatic evaluations.

A humanitarian emergency was defined as a calamitous situation, of either natural (including famine, flooding (localised or widespread), storms, cyclones, earthquake, tsunami) or anthropogenic origin (may include widespread (i.e. affecting whole regions/countries) or geographically confined conflict (i.e. affecting only parts of a country/or multiple countries, e.g. the West African Islamic terrorist crisis affecting border regions of Mali, Niger, Nigeria, Burkina Faso, Cameroon and Chad), or persecution of a specific ethnic group (e.g. Bosnian, Rohingya and Rwanda genocides), in which the functioning of a community or society (whether a subsection or whole population) was severely disrupted, causing human suffering and material loss that exceeded the affected population's ability to cope using its own resources⁴. Studies with military personnel or peacekeepers, in demilitarized zones, with migrant, tribal or nomadic populations or temporary/seasonal labourers (e.g. forest or dam workers, gold or gem miners) were excluded because these contexts may not include other characteristics, specific to humanitarian emergencies, such as breakdown of health services and lack of concurrent infectious diseases, malnutrition and anaemia, which may influence vector control tool efficacy. A detailed study protocol is available from²⁷.

Data analysis

Two review authors independently extracted information from eligible studies, without masking to author or publication, into a pre-piloted database. Disagreements in data extraction were resolved by discussion and consensus between the two review authors with arbitration by a third, when necessary. Original study authors and research groups were contacted in cases of missing data or ambiguous reporting. We extracted data on

the following: (1) study design: type of study, method of participant selection, sample size, details of sampling methodology, including number of time points. For cluster-RCTs (cRCTs): adjustment for clustering, number of clusters, size of buffer zones, unit of randomization, intra-cluster correlation coefficient (ICC) and follow-up period. (2) participants: study settings, including humanitarian emergency phase, context (displacement dynamics, mobility, political and logistical considerations) and camp/settlement structure (road access and condition), population characteristics, including age, gender, ethnicity, socio-economic status, methods and rates of recruitment, withdrawal, and loss to follow-up. (3) intervention: full details of intervention and any co-interventions and any theory informing it, coverage of intervention and any co-interventions, compliance of intervention and any co-interventions, mechanism(s) of intervention and co-intervention deployment, cost and associated resource requirements. (4) all outcomes: definition of outcome, diagnostic method or surveillance method, passive or active case detection, duration of follow-up, time points at which outcomes were assessed, number of events, number of participants or unit time, statistical power, unit of analysis, factors adjusted for, incomplete outcomes/missing data, *Plasmodium* species. (5) entomological outcomes: primary and secondary vector(s) species, vector(s) behaviour (adult habitat, peak biting times, exophilic/endophilic (indoor/outdoor resting, respectively), endophagic/exophagic (indoor/outdoor biting, respectively), anthropophilic/zoophilic (human or animal biting, respectively)), method(s) of collection, malaria endemicity, insecticide resistance status, sporozoite rate per parasite species, bloodmeal index and vector parity. (6) other: intervention durability or residual efficacy adverse events, user acceptability and other unintended effects.

Analyses were structured first by type of vector control intervention, second by outcome (separating *P. falciparum* and *P. vivax*), and third by study design. If a combination of vector control interventions were used (e.g. IRS with ITNs), these were considered as separate interventions. Studies that reported sufficient data to calculate crude effects and studies that reported crude or adjusted effect measures with 95% confidence intervals (CI) were included in the quantitative analysis.

Epidemiological data were combined in meta-analyses. Meta-analyses of both crude and adjusted results were reported. Random effects models were used to calculate pooled effect measures (risk ratios (RRs) for randomised controlled trials, odds ratios (ORs) for dichotomous outcomes in non-randomised studies and incidence rate ratios (IRRs) for clinical malaria incidence in non-randomised studies. Study effects were combined in the meta-analysis using the generic inverse method for non-randomised studies with adjusted results. Characteristics of included studies were presented in tables (Appendix: supplementary table 3 and 4).

Risk of bias for randomised controlled trials was assessed using the Cochrane 'Risk of bias' tool²⁸. Risk of bias for non-randomised studies was assessed using the Newcastle-Ottawa Scale (NOS)²⁹. There were insufficient studies identified to assess publication bias; however, we had planned to assess this by visual inspection of funnel plots and Egger test for funnel plot asymmetry³⁰. Certainty of the evidence was evaluated for all comparisons using the Grading of Recommendations, Assessment, Development and Evaluation (GRADE) approach³¹.

Analyses were performed with Review Manager 5.4.1³². This study is registered with PROSPERO, CRD42020214961.

Role of the funding source

The funder of the study had no role in study design, data collection, data analysis, data interpretation, or writing of the report. The corresponding author had full access to all the data in the study and had final responsibility for the decision to submit for publication.

Figure 1. Study selection

Results

Our initial search yielded 21,309 records of which 12,475 remained after removing duplicates (Figure 1). Twenty-four records were considered for inclusion, and of these 22 contained the necessary data for inclusion in the quantitative analysis (Appendix: supplementary table 3 and 4). One record was excluded from the quantitative analysis because it was a study with zero events³³, while the other was excluded because it lacked a true control group¹⁰. All studies were conducted between 1989 and 2018 in chronic/protracted humanitarian emergencies (n=22/22) in 9 countries; 5 in sub-Saharan Africa, 2 in the Eastern Mediterranean and 2 in South-East Asia (Figure 2). Sources of all humanitarian emergencies were violent conflict, usually due to political/religious/ethnic persecution. Seven different vector control interventions were deployed alone (n=21/22) or in combination (n=1/22): ITNs^{6,8,33-44}, IRS^{9,45,46}, insecticide-treated plastic sheeting¹¹, insecticide-treated *chaddars*¹³, insecticide-treated clothing¹⁷, topical repellents^{21,47} and insecticidal treatment of livestock²³ (Appendix: supplementary table 3 and 4). Nine studies were either cRCTs (n=6/9) (either household-randomised or village-randomised) or randomized trials at the individual-level (n=3/9). Thirteen studies were non-randomized, including a before-after study (n=1/13), controlled before-after studies (n=1/13), cross-sectional surveys (n=7/13), cross-sectional surveys with nested case-control studies (n=2/13), a cohort trial (n=1/13) and a non-randomized trial (n=1/13). Where appropriate, for cRCTs the data were adjusted for clustering and sensitivity analyses were performed for outcomes where the ICC was estimated. For all outcomes, the sensitivity analyses showed that using an estimated ICC did not greatly influence the effect size (Appendix: supplementary table 5).

Figure 2. Geographical distribution of included studies.

The majority of studies included in the meta-analysis (n=13/22) evaluated ITNs^{6,8,33-44}, demonstrating a significant reduction in *P. falciparum* case incidence (RR 0.55 [95% CI: 0.37-0.79], four cRCTs; high certainty), *P. vivax* case incidence (RR 0.69 [95% CI: 0.51-0.94], three cRCTs; moderate certainty) and *P. falciparum* prevalence (RR 0.60 [95% CI: 0.40-0.88], two cRCTs; high certainty) over 10 months, in randomised trials conducted during humanitarian emergencies on the Thai-Myanmar border^{34,35}, in interior Myanmar⁸ and Pakistan³⁶ (Table 1). Four studies deployed IRS, with evidence from observational studies in Pakistan supporting an impact on *P. falciparum* incidence (rate ratio 0.57 [95% CI: 0.53-0.61]; one cross-sectional study; very low certainty)⁴⁵, *P. vivax* incidence (rate ratio 0.51 [95% CI: 0.49-0.52]; one cross-sectional study; very low certainty)⁴⁵ and prevalence (OR 0.74 [95% CI: 0.25-2.14]; two cross-sectional studies; very low certainty)^{41,45} (Table 1). However, the only cRCT to evaluate IRS in eastern Sudan did not observe an effect on *P. falciparum* prevalence (RR 1.31 [95% CI: 0.91-1.88]; low certainty)⁹ (Table 1). Furthermore, a single cross-sectional study in Pakistan demonstrated a combined effect of ITNs and IRS on *P. vivax* prevalence (OR 0.26 [95% CI: 0.10-0.67]; very low certainty)⁴¹ (Table 1). The use of topical repellents was also associated with a significant decrease in *P. falciparum* infection incidence (RR 0.58 [95% CI: 0.35-0.97], moderate certainty) but not *P. vivax* infection incidence (RR 1.06 [95% CI: 0.60-1.85]; low certainty), in two cRCTs conducted in Pakistan and Thailand^{21,47}.

Figure 3. The effect of ITNs on (A) *P. falciparum* case incidence or (B) *P. vivax* case incidence. Dolan 1993 is subdivided into study camps with low (top entry) and high (bottom entry) *P. falciparum* incidence. Error bars show 95% CIs. df=degrees of freedom. M-H=Mantel-Haenszel.

Figure 4. The effect of IRS on (A) *P. falciparum* malaria incidence or (B) *P. vivax* malaria incidence. Error bars show 95% CIs. df=degrees of freedom. M-H=Mantel-Haenszel.

Figure 5. The effect of topical repellents on *P. falciparum* or *P. vivax* infection incidence. Error bars show 95% CIs. df=degrees of freedom. M-H=Mantel-Haenszel.

The remaining studies evaluated vector control interventions, specifically designed for use during humanitarian emergencies. Individual studies demonstrated an impact of insecticide-treated plastic sheeting on *P. falciparum* case incidence over four months (RR 0.56 [95% CI: 0.39-0.80]; one cohort study; very low certainty) in Sierra Leone¹¹, and of insecticide-treated clothing on *P. falciparum* prevalence (OR 0.29 [95% CI: 0.14-

0.60]; one non-randomized study; very low certainty) in Kenya¹⁷. In addition, insecticide-treated *chaddars* reduced *P. falciparum* case incidence (RR 0.56 [95% CI: 0.39-0.80]; moderate certainty) and *P. vivax* case incidence (RR 0.74 [95% CI: 0.54-1.02]; low certainty) and insecticide-treated cattle significantly impacted both *P. falciparum* (rate ratio 0.44 [95% CI: 0.22-0.86]; moderate certainty, and RR 0.46 [95% CI: 0.31-0.70]; high certainty) and *P. vivax* incidence and prevalence (rate ratio 0.69 [95% CI: 0.50-0.95] and RR 0.60 [95% CI: 0.33-1.08]; both moderate certainty), respectively) in Pakistan in two cRCTs^{13,23}.

Regarding secondary outcomes, anaemia was measured in five studies, with ITNs having a moderate effect on haemoglobin levels (RR 0.95 [95% CI: 0.81-1.11]; one cRCT in Myanmar⁸ and mean difference -0.10 [95% CI: -0.34-0.14]; a cross-sectional survey in Uganda⁶); ITPS also decreased anaemia prevalence [mean difference 0.71 [0.48-0.94]; one cohort study in Sierra Leone¹¹). By comparison topical repellents had no impact on anaemia prevalence (RR 1.06 [95%CI: 0.91-1.23]; one cRCT in Thailand⁴⁷). There was insufficient published data for all other secondary outcomes to perform quantitative analyses.

Due to the absence of a published protocol for all studies, there were some concerns regarding the risk of bias in the selection of the reported result for RCTs. However, in all other domains the risk of bias was low for all studies apart from Rowland 1999¹³, where additionally there were concerns related to bias due to deviations from the intended intervention. (Appendix: supplementary table 7). There was a high risk of bias in two case-control studies, which were scored low on the NOS in the presentiveness of cases, selection of controls and ascertainment of exposure (Appendix: supplementary table 8). There was a moderate risk of bias for the 11 cross-sectional studies; bias was attributed to the lack of information on non-respondents, exposures not being formally validated through a measurement tool and that some studies did not control for any potential confounders (Appendix: supplementary table 9). Finally, there was a low risk of bias in the one cohort study (Appendix: supplementary table 10). There were insufficient studies to test for asymmetry in the meta-analysis for any outcome measurement per intervention. The GRADE assessments indicated moderate to high certainty evidence for the effect of ITNs, insecticide-treated *chaddars*, topical repellents and insecticide-treated cattle on malaria outcomes during humanitarian emergencies (Table 1). The GRADE approach indicated very low to low certainty evidence for the effect of IRS, IRS + ITNs, insecticide-treated clothing and insecticide-treated plastic sheeting on malaria outcomes during humanitarian emergencies (Table 1).

Table 1. GRADE quality of evidence for the impact of insecticide-treated nets on malaria disease burden during humanitarian emergencies.

ITNs compared to no ITNs for preventing malaria												
Patient or population: refugees/IDPs affected by humanitarian emergencies												
Setting: humanitarian emergencies in Myanmar, Pakistan and the Thai-Myanmar border												
Intervention: ITNs												
Comparison: no ITNs												
Outcomes	Anticipated absolute effects (95% CI)			Relative effect (95% CI)	Number of participants/person-years (studies)	Quality of the Evidence					Certainty of the Evidence (GRADE)	Text summary
	No ITNs	ITNs	Risk difference with ITNs			Risk of bias	Inconsistency	Indirectness	Imprecision	Other considerations		
<i>P. falciparum</i> case incidence	70 per 1000	39 per 1000	32 fewer per 1000 (44 fewer to 15 fewer)	RR 0.55 (0.37 to 0.79)	3200 (4 RCTs)	Not serious	Not serious	Not serious	Serious ^a	Strong association	⊕⊕⊕⊕ HIGH, downgraded due to serious imprecision. Upgraded due to large magnitude of effect.	ITNs result in large reduction in <i>P. falciparum</i> case incidence.
<i>P. falciparum</i> prevalence	37 per 1000	22 per 1000	15 fewer per 1000 (22 fewer to 4 fewer)	RR 0.60 (0.40 to 0.88)	2079 (2 RCTs)	Not serious	Not serious	Not serious	Serious ^a	Strong association	⊕⊕⊕⊕ HIGH, downgraded due to serious imprecision. Upgraded due to large magnitude of effect.	ITNs result in large reduction in <i>P. falciparum</i> prevalence.
<i>P. vivax</i> case incidence	116 per 1000	80 per 1000	36 fewer per 1000 (57 fewer to 7 fewer)	RR 0.69 (0.51 to 0.94)	2997 (3 RCTs)	Not serious	Not serious	Not serious	Serious ^a	None	⊕⊕⊕○ MODERATE, due to serious imprecision.	ITNs likely reduces <i>P. vivax</i> case incidence.
<i>P. vivax</i> prevalence	99 per 1000	99 per 1000	0 fewer per 1000 (25 fewer to 34 more)	RR 1.00 (0.75 to 1.34)	2079 (2 RCTs)	Not serious	Not serious	Not serious	Very serious ^{a,b}	None	⊕⊕○○ LOW, due to very serious imprecision.	ITNs may result in little to no difference in <i>P. vivax</i> prevalence.

a. Downgraded by 1 for imprecision: the effect estimate had wide confidence intervals.

b. Downgraded by 1 for imprecision: there is uncertainty about the magnitude of effect of the intervention, as it fails to exclude benefit or harm.

Table 2. GRADE quality of evidence for the impact of indoor residual spraying on malaria disease burden during humanitarian emergencies.

IRS compared to no IRS for preventing malaria												
Patient or population: refugees/IDPs affected by humanitarian emergencies												
Setting: humanitarian emergencies in Sudan and Pakistan												
Intervention: IRS												
Comparison: no IRS												
Outcomes	Anticipated absolute effects (95% CI)			Relative effect (95% CI)	Number of participants/person-years (studies)	Quality of the Evidence					Certainty of the Evidence (GRADE)	Text Summary
	No IRS	IRS	Risk difference with IRS			Risk of bias	Inconsistency	Indirectness	Imprecision	Other considerations		
<i>P. falciparum</i> incidence	7 per 1000	4 per 1000	3 fewer per 1000 (3 fewer to 3 fewer)	Rate ratio¹ 0.57 (0.53-0.61)	480,377 (1 observational study)	Serious ^a	Not serious	Serious ^b	Not serious	All plausible residual confounding would reduce the demonstrated effect	⊕○○○ VERY LOW, due to serious risk of bias and serious indirectness. Upgraded because all plausible confounding would reduce the demonstrated effect.	The evidence is very uncertain about the effect of IRS on <i>P. falciparum</i> incidence.
<i>P. falciparum</i> prevalence	257 per 1000	337 per 1000	80 more per 1000 (23 fewer to 226 more)	RR 1.31 (0.91-1.88)	278 (1 RCT)	Not serious	Not serious	Not serious	Very serious ^{a,c}	None	⊕⊕○○ LOW, due to very serious imprecision.	IRS may result in little to no difference in <i>P. falciparum</i> prevalence.
<i>P. vivax</i> incidence	57 per 1000	29 per 1000	28 fewer per 1000 (28 fewer to 28 fewer)	Rate ratio¹ 0.51 (0.49-0.52)	480,372 (1 observational study)	Serious ^a	Not serious	Serious ^b	Not serious	All plausible residual confounding would reduce the demonstrated effect	⊕○○○ VERY LOW, due to serious risk of bias and serious indirectness. Upgraded because all plausible confounding would reduce the demonstrated effect.	The evidence is very uncertain about the effect of IRS on <i>P. vivax</i> incidence.
<i>P. vivax</i> prevalence	78 per 1000	59 per 1000	19 fewer per 1000 (57 fewer)	OR 0.74 (0.25-2.14)	4,708 (2 observational studies)	Serious ^a	Serious ^d	Serious ^e	Serious ^f	Strong association; all plausible	⊕○○○ VERY LOW, due to serious risk of bias, serious	The evidence is very uncertain about the effect of IRS on <i>P. vivax</i> prevalence.

			to 75 more)							residual confounding would reduce the demonstrated effect	inconsistency, serious indirectness and serious imprecision. Upgraded because all plausible confounding would reduce the demonstrated effect.	
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1. Rate ratio based on incidence per 1000 population for the periods April-December of 1993 and 1994

- a. Downgrade by 1 for risk of bias: all studies were non-randomised, observational and had a moderate to high risk of bias according to the Newcastle Ottawa Scale.
- b. Downgraded by 1 for indirectness: only one study was included, and was conducted in Pakistan. The results may not be generalisable to other settings.
- c. Downgraded by 1 for indirectness: only two studies were included, and both were conducted in Pakistan. The results may not be generalisable to other settings.
- d. Downgraded by 1 for inconsistency: minimal overlap of confidence intervals and considerable heterogeneity ($I^2 = 81\%$, $p = 0.02$).
- e. Downgraded by 1 for imprecision: the effect estimate had very wide confidence intervals.
- f. Downgraded by 1 for imprecision: there is uncertainty about the magnitude of effect of the intervention, as it fails to exclude benefit or harm.

Table 3. GRADE quality of evidence for the impact of insecticide-treated spraying and indoor residual spraying on malaria disease burden during humanitarian emergencies.

IRS + ITNs compared to no IRS + ITNs for preventing malaria												
Patient or population: refugees/IDPs affected by humanitarian emergencies												
Setting: humanitarian emergency in Pakistan												
Intervention: IRS + ITNs												
Comparison: no IRS + ITNs												
Outcomes	Anticipated absolute effects (95% CI)			Relative effect (95% CI)	Number of participants/per son-years (studies)	Quality of the Evidence					Certainty of the Evidence (GRADE)	Text Summary
	No IRS + ITNs	IRS + ITNs	Risk difference with IRS + ITNs			Risk of bias	Inconsistency	Indirectness	Imprecision	Other considerations		
<i>P. vivax</i> prevalence	64 per 1000	17 per 1000	46 fewer per 1000 (57 fewer to 20 fewer)	OR 0.26 (0.10-0.67)	805 (1 observational study)	Serious ^a	Not serious	Serious ^b	Not serious	All plausible residual confounding would reduce the demonstrated effect	⊕○○○ VERY LOW, due to serious risk of bias and serious indirectness. Upgraded because all plausible confounding would reduce the demonstrated effect.	The evidence is very uncertain about the effect of ITNs and IRS on <i>P. vivax</i> prevalence.

a. Downgraded by 1 for risk of bias: all studies were non-randomised, observational and had a moderate to high risk of bias according to the Newcastle Ottawa Scale b. Downgraded by 1 for indirectness: only one study was included, which was conducted in Pakistan. The results may not be generalisable to other settings.

Table 4. GRADE quality of evidence for the impact of insecticide-treated clothing on malaria disease burden during humanitarian emergencies.

Insecticide-treated clothing compared to no insecticide-treated clothing for preventing malaria												
Patient or population: refugees/IDPs affected by humanitarian emergencies Setting: humanitarian emergency in Kenya Intervention: insecticide-treated clothing Comparison: no insecticide-treated clothing												
Outcomes	Anticipated absolute effects (95% CI)			Relative effect (95% CI)	Number of participants/person-years (studies)	Quality of the Evidence					Certainty of the Evidence (GRADE)	Text Summary
	No insecticide-treated clothing	Insecticide-treated clothing	Risk difference with insecticide-treated clothing			Risk of bias	Inconsistency	Indirectness	Imprecision	Other considerations		
<i>P. falciparum</i> prevalence	659 per 1000	359 per 1000	284 fewer per 1000 (412 fewer to 130 fewer)	OR 0.29 (0.14-0.60)	181 (1 observational study)	Serious ^a	Not serious	Serious ^b	Not serious	All plausible residual confounding would reduce the demonstrated effect	⊕○○○ VERY LOW, due to serious risk of bias and serious indirectness. Upgraded because all plausible confounding would reduce the demonstrated effect.	The evidence is very uncertain about the effect of insecticide-treated clothing on <i>P. falciparum</i> .

a. Downgraded by 1 for risk of bias: all studies were non-randomised, observational and had a moderate to high risk of bias according to the Newcastle Ottawa Scale

b. Downgraded by 1 for indirectness: only one study was included, which was conducted in Kenya. The results may not be generalisable to other settings.

Table 5. GRADE quality of evidence for the impact of insecticide-treated plastic sheeting on malaria disease burden during humanitarian emergencies.

Insecticide-treated plastic sheeting compared to no insecticide-treated plastic sheeting for preventing malaria												
Patient or population: refugees/IDPs affected by humanitarian emergencies												
Setting: humanitarian emergency in Sierra Leone												
Intervention: insecticide-treated plastic sheeting												
Comparison: no insecticide-treated plastic sheeting												
Outcomes	Anticipated absolute effects (95% CI)			Relative effect (95% CI)	Number of participants/person-years (studies)	Quality of the Evidence					Certainty of the Evidence (GRADE)	Text Summary
	No insecticide-treated plastic sheeting	Insecticide-treated plastic sheeting	Risk difference with insecticide-treated plastic sheeting			Risk of bias	Inconsistency	Indirectness	Imprecision	Other considerations		
<i>P. falciparum</i> incidence	4 per 1000	3 per 1000	1 fewer per 1000 (1 fewer to 1 fewer)	Rate ratio¹ 0.68 (0.62-0.74)	31,023 (1 observational study)	Serious ^a	Not serious	Serious ^b	Not serious	All plausible residual confounding would reduce the demonstrated effect	⊕○○○ VERY LOW, due to serious risk of bias and serious indirectness. Upgraded because all plausible confounding would reduce the demonstrated effect.	The evidence is very uncertain about the effect of insecticide-treated plastic sheeting on <i>P. falciparum</i> incidence.
<i>P. falciparum</i> prevalence	514 per 1000	458 per 1000	56 fewer per 1000 (110 fewer to 0 fewer)	OR 0.80 (0.64-1.00)	1,610 (1 observational study)	Serious ^a	Not serious	Serious ^b	Serious ^c	All plausible residual confounding would reduce the demonstrated effect	⊕○○○ VERY LOW, due to serious risk of bias, serious indirectness and serious imprecision. Upgraded because all plausible confounding would reduce the demonstrated effect.	The evidence is very uncertain about the effect of insecticide-treated plastic sheeting on <i>P. falciparum</i> prevalence.

1. Rate ratio based on incidence per 100 child-years at risk

a. Downgraded by 1 for risk of bias: all studies were non-randomised and observational.

b. Downgraded by 1 for indirectness: only one study was included, which was conducted in Sierra Leone. The results may not be generalisable to other settings.

c. Downgraded by 1 for imprecision: there is uncertainty about the magnitude of effect of the intervention, as it fails to exclude benefit or harm.

Table 6. GRADE quality of evidence for the impact of insecticide-treated cattle on malaria disease burden during humanitarian emergencies.

Insecticide-treated cattle compared to no insecticide-treated cattle for preventing malaria												
Patient or population: refugees/IDPs affected by humanitarian emergencies												
Setting: humanitarian emergency in Pakistan												
Intervention: insecticide-treated cattle												
Comparison: no insecticide-treated cattle												
Outcomes	Anticipated absolute effects (95% CI)			Relative effect (95% CI)	Number of participants/person-years (studies)	Quality of the Evidence					Certainty of the Evidence (GRADE)	Text Summary
	No insecticide-treated cattle	Insecticide-treated cattle	Risk difference with insecticide-treated cattle			Risk of bias	Inconsistency	Indirectness	Imprecision	Other considerations		
<i>P. falciparum</i> incidence	11 per 1000	5 per 1000	6 fewer per 1000 (6 fewer to 6 fewer)	Rate ratio 0.44 (0.22-0.86)	93,535 (1 RCT)	Not serious	Not serious	Not serious	Serious ^a	None	⊕⊕⊕○ MODERATE, due to serious imprecision.	Insecticide-treated cattle likely results in a large reduction in <i>P. falciparum</i> incidence.
<i>P. falciparum</i> prevalence	19 per 1000	9 per 1000	10 fewer per 1000 (13 fewer to 6 fewer)	RR 0.46 (0.31-0.70)	19,152 (1 RCT)	Not serious	Not serious	Not serious	Not serious	None	⊕⊕⊕⊕ HIGH	Insecticide-treated cattle results in large reduction in <i>P. falciparum</i> prevalence.
<i>P. vivax</i> incidence	72 per 1000	50 per 1000	22 fewer per 1000 (22 fewer to 22 fewer)	Rate ratio 0.69 (0.50 to 0.95)	93,535 (1 RCT)	Not serious	Not serious	Not serious	Serious ^a	None	⊕⊕⊕○ MODERATE, due to serious imprecision.	Insecticide-treated cattle likely results in a large reduction in <i>P. vivax</i> incidence.
<i>P. vivax</i> prevalence	82 per 1000	49 per 1000	33 fewer per 1000 (55 fewer to 7 more)	RR 0.60 (0.33-1.08)	19,152 (1 RCT)	Not serious	Not serious	Not serious	Serious ^b	None	⊕⊕⊕○ MODERATE, due to serious imprecision.	Insecticide-treated cattle may result in a large reduction in <i>P. vivax</i> prevalence.

a. Downgraded by 1 for imprecision: CIs span from a small effect to a large effect.

b. Downgraded by 1 for imprecision: CIs include both a large effect and no effect.

Table 7. GRADE quality of evidence for the impact of insecticide-treated *chaddars* on malaria disease burden during humanitarian emergencies.

Insecticide-treated <i>chaddars</i> compared to no insecticide-treated <i>chaddars</i> for preventing malaria												
Patient or population: refugees/IDPs affected by humanitarian emergencies												
Setting: humanitarian emergency in Pakistan												
Intervention: insecticide-treated <i>chaddars</i>												
Comparison: no insecticide-treated <i>chaddars</i>												
Outcomes	Anticipated absolute effects (95% CI)			Relative effect (95% CI)	Number of participants/person-years (studies)	Quality of the Evidence					Certainty of the Evidence (GRADE)	Text Summary
	No insecticide-treated <i>chaddars</i>	Insecticide-treated <i>chaddars</i>	Risk difference with insecticide-treated <i>chaddars</i>			Risk of bias	Inconsistency	Indirectness	Imprecision	Other considerations		
<i>P. falciparum</i> case incidence	116 per 1000	65 per 1000	51 fewer per 1000 (71 fewer to 23 fewer)	RR 0.56 (0.39-0.80)	682 (1 RCT)	Not serious	Not serious	Not serious	Serious ^a	None	⊕⊕⊕○ MODERATE, due to serious imprecision.	Insecticide-treated <i>chaddars</i> /top-sheets likely results in a large reduction in <i>P. falciparum</i> case incidence.
<i>P. vivax</i> case incidence	222 per 1000	164 per 1000	58 fewer per 1000 (102 fewer to 4 more)	RR 0.74 (0.54-1.02)	682 (1 RCT)	Not serious	Not serious	Not serious	Very serious ^b	None	⊕⊕○○ LOW, due to very serious imprecision.	Insecticide-treated <i>chaddars</i> /top-sheets may reduce <i>P. vivax</i> case incidence.

a. Downgraded by 1 for imprecision: the effect estimate had wide confidence intervals.

b. Downgraded by 2: very wide confidence intervals indicating that the true effect could be large or there could be no effect.

Table 8. GRADE quality of evidence for the impact of topical repellents on malaria disease burden during humanitarian emergencies.

Topical repellents compared to no topical repellents for preventing malaria												
Patient or population: refugees/IDPs affected by humanitarian emergencies												
Setting: humanitarian emergencies in Pakistan and Thailand												
Intervention: topical repellents												
Comparison: no topical repellents												
Outcomes	Anticipated absolute effects (95% CI)			Relative effect (95% CI)	Number of participants/person-years (studies)	Quality of the Evidence					Certainty of the Evidence (GRADE)	Text Summary
	No topical repellents	Topical repellents	Risk difference with topical repellents			Risk of bias	Inconsistency	Indirectness	Imprecision	Other considerations		
<i>P. falciparum</i> infection incidence	71 per 1000	41 per 1000	30 fewer per 1000 (46 fewer to 2 fewer)	RR 0.58 (0.35-0.97)	1822 (2 RCTs)	Not serious	Not serious	Not serious	Very serious ^a	Strong association	⊕⊕⊕○ MODERATE, due to very serious imprecision. Upgraded due to large magnitude of effect.	Topical repellents likely reduce <i>P. falciparum</i> infection incidence.
<i>P. vivax</i> infection incidence	188 per 1000	199 per 1000	11 more per 1000 (75 fewer to 160 more)	RR 1.06 (0.60-1.85)	1822 (2 RCTs)	Not serious	Not serious	Not serious	Very serious ^{a,b}	None	⊕⊕○○ LOW, due to very serious imprecision.	Topical repellents may result in little to no difference in <i>P. vivax</i> infection incidence.

a. Downgraded by 2 due to imprecision: the effect estimate had very large confidence intervals

b. Downgraded by 1 due to imprecision: there is uncertainty about the magnitude of effect of the intervention, as it fails to exclude benefit or harm.

Discussion

Study findings showed high certainty evidence that ITN deployment in chronic humanitarian emergencies can reduce *P. falciparum* and *P. vivax* incidence by 45% and 31%, respectively. Similar effect sizes have been reported from recent meta-analyses of ITNs and long-lasting insecticidal nets (LLINs) used in non-emergency settings in endemic parts of Africa⁴⁸. The contemporary effectiveness of ITNs is predicated on several factors, including net access, use, retention, bioefficacy, durability and vector population susceptibility⁴⁹. Several operational studies have highlighted significant pragmatic barriers to ITN use in mobile populations of IDPs, including inadequate sleeping arrangements (e.g. use of multiple sleeping places, sleeping outside, lack of beds/mattresses and places to hang nets), over-crowding, violence, mis-use of ITNs (e.g. using nets for fishing or housing materials), rapid development of net holes from harsh living conditions and insufficient IEC/BCC (information education communication/behaviour change communication) activities^{6,37,50,51}. Unfavorable characteristics of ITNs themselves have also been reported, which may be exacerbated in emergencies if there is an immediate need for their use; ITNs may be hung without following the manufacturer's instructions to wash and dry for 24-48 hours, causing unpleasant odors or chemical irritation^{37,52}. Another complication of deploying personal protective vector control interventions is the economic vulnerability of IDPs relative to neighbouring communities and host communities, which can encourage trade in donated goods, including ITNs, influx of untreated or unrecommended ITNs into local clandestine markets, or in some cases theft, heightened tensions and even political violence against IDPs by those who were not beneficiaries of these charitable commodities^{37,50}. Adapted ITN delivery mechanisms and coordinated monitoring and evaluation programmes, in particular, accurate population mapping, continuous community-based distribution systems, hang-up campaigns reinforcing key IEC/BCC messages, and strengthened intersectoral partnerships, are crucial to achieve and maintain high ITN coverage and use during humanitarian emergencies⁵⁰.

There were some indications that IRS can control *P. falciparum* and *P. vivax* incidence rates during humanitarian emergencies, however, the certainty of the evidence was very low, aligning with previous results from non-emergency settings, which highlighted the need for additional trials to quantify the effect size of IRS in different transmission settings⁵³. Based on proven ITN and IRS efficacy during non-emergency situations, the WHO has previously recommended these two tools for use in complex emergencies and our study findings strengthen and support this policy for ITNs, where shelter types and sleeping arrangements are appropriate for their use. One advantage that IRS has over ITNs is that little/no behaviour changes are required, which can impede intervention use during humanitarian emergencies. IRS can also have collateral benefits of reducing populations of other disease vectors (e.g. sandflies⁵⁴), as well as perceived

effects on nuisance insects and pests⁵⁵. However, IRS does require greater logistical resources for implementation compared to ITNs, including stable, concentrated shelter structures for insecticide treatment and sustained donor initiatives. One strategy to circumvent some of these limitations has been to exploit utilitarian emergency materials, such as plastic sheeting, tarpaulins, and tents, as longer-term mechanisms of insecticide delivery in emergencies^{10,12,20,56-60}. While laboratory and phase II entomological studies suggest that these experimental interventions can control malaria vector populations^{10,20,58-62}, this systematic review only identified one study which reported very low certainty evidence of an impact of insecticide-treated plastic sheeting on *P. falciparum* case incidence in West Africa during a chronic emergency¹¹. This concept has also been extended to treating personal material items during emergencies, including clothing, blankets and bedsheets, with pyrethroid insecticides^{13,15,17,63}, with moderate evidence for a reduction in *P. falciparum* case incidence from a household-randomised trial of permethrin-treated *chaddars* in Pakistan¹³ and lower certainty evidence for insecticide-treated clothing to prevent malaria infection in Kenya¹⁷. As none of these products are currently commercially available any longer, there is a clear and urgent need to design and further evaluate novel, innovative, emergency-specific vector control tools, to complement LLIN distributions and IRS campaigns. Considerations must be given for how best to engage with the private sector and stimulate the development of these 'niche' vector control tools, particularly those which may not have a market share for routine use in stable malaria endemic settings⁶⁴.

Two other vector control tools, topical repellents and insecticide-treated cattle, were also associated with significant reductions in malaria incidence in the Eastern Mediterranean and South-East Asia with moderate to high certainty evidence^{21,23,47}. However, by comparison to sub-Saharan Africa, there are key differences in malaria vector populations between these areas, particularly exophilic/exophagic and anthropophilic/zoophilic tendencies, which may influence the efficacy of these vector control interventions, which specifically target these behaviours. Insecticide-treated cattle was an effective intervention in Pakistan^{23,65} where vector populations (*Anopheles stephensi*, *An. culicifacies*, *An. subpictus*, *An. fluviatilis* and *An. annularis*) are highly zoophilic; it could be assumed that this strategy would also show promise in areas where *An. arabiensis* is a major vector species in sub-Saharan Africa, but perhaps not where *An. gambiae* s.s., *An. coluzzii* or *An. funestus* predominate⁶⁶⁻⁶⁸. Topical repellents have not always performed well in malaria endemic parts of Africa, largely due to issues of standardised repellent use, user compliance and duration of protection, which can all contribute to participants being unprotected at peak vector biting times during the night and early morning^{69,70}. Differences in vector behaviour were also apparent in some of the eligible ITN studies from South-East Asia, where the evidence

for an effect of ITNs on malaria transmission is weak in rural, non-conflict areas due to early biting and exophilic/exophagic behaviours of most primary vectors^{71,72}; a similar lack of protection from malaria was observed in populations of IDPs in the same region⁸.

Generating robust evidence for the effectiveness of vector control tools in humanitarian emergencies is complicated by a number of fundamental features of these situations. It is very challenging to design prospective studies during emergencies due to their unpredictability. The rapid speed of emergency onset may prohibit collection of baseline data, study protocol design, ethical approval, study site mapping and appropriate trial arm stratification. Furthermore, trial design in terms of control arms is complex because it is not necessarily ethical to distribute vector control interventions inequitably during an emergency, especially where the malaria burden is high. Vector control activities in refugee camps are usually accompanied by increased access to malaria diagnosis and treatment and other healthcare services. Effect sizes of a particular vector control intervention may be overestimated because they are difficult to disentangle from coincident improvements in other preventative and curative measures. Resource allocation is assumed to be balanced across displaced populations (in both treatment and control groups), but this is unlikely to be a reality, and systematic supporting data are not reported; nor are they routinely collected for other confounding factors, such as food insecurity, lack of access to basic WASH facilities, and prevalence of non-malaria febrile illnesses such as dengue, respiratory tract infections, including pneumonia and SARS-CoV-2, diarrheal diseases and malnutrition^{39,73}. Infrastructure in refugee/displacement camps and affected communities may also be highly heterogeneous, especially in acute settings; road access, variation in camp shelters or house construction, waste management and water drainage systems, and local political and logistical issues will all impact feasibility and protective efficacy of deployed vector control interventions.

In this systematic review and meta-analysis, in several cases published data were limited to observational studies or retrospective programmatic evaluations^{6,37-39,41-43,45,46}, or from randomised studies, which were undertaken in much more stable IDP settlements, that were established for a number of years^{8,9,13,22,23,34-36,47}. We were only able to identify one acute study, during a tropical cyclone in Vanuatu, and this study was excluded because it had zero malaria events³³. Given the difficulties associated with deploying and monitoring vector control tools in very early-stage emergencies, if longer-term, protracted crises stabilize and then regress, depending on the complex factors contributing to the emergency, these may present valuable opportunities to develop evidence for malaria vector control tool efficacy in simulated acute-stage conditions⁷⁴. Furthermore, the recent revision of evidence criteria for vector control tools by the newly

established Vector Control Advisory Group (VCAG)⁷⁵, now requires two cRCTs with epidemiological endpoints, *in lieu* of previous recommendations based on entomological studies, presenting an additional significant barrier for the evaluation of novel interventions during humanitarian emergencies⁷⁶.

The available literature reviewed by this study also suffered from other limitations. Most eligible randomized studies were conducted in chronic complex emergencies in the Eastern Mediterranean and in South-East Asia, with comparatively fewer from sub-Saharan Africa, where most of the malaria disease burden is now concentrated³. In addition, the majority of eligible studies were undertaken between 1990-mid 2000s and due to their age, some key details, for example, reporting methods of cluster randomization, were not always described adequately because of the available reporting guidelines at the time, thereby downgrading their overall GRADE assessment⁷⁷. Furthermore, all eligible studies evaluated interventions using insecticides (primarily pyrethroids) which may no longer be effective for malaria vector control due to widespread insecticide resistance⁷⁸⁻⁸⁰. New dual active ingredient LLINs, piperonyl-butoxide LLINs and novel IRS compounds are undergoing phase III trials in non-emergency settings to determine their efficacy against pyrethroid-resistant malaria vector populations⁸¹⁻⁸⁵. In addition to evaluating the efficacy of these new tools, and other existing ones in emergencies, additional randomised data spanning a range of geographical areas, malaria vector species and insecticide resistance intensities are also warranted to strengthen the evidence basis for use of vector control tools to prevent malaria during humanitarian emergencies.

Contributors

LAM and MR conceived of the study concept. LAM, JFA, BP and MR developed the study design. LAM, JFA, KC, BP and LP screened the literature and extracted data from the articles. JFA and KC led the data analysis, with support from LAM, BP, LP and MR. LAM wrote the first draft of the manuscript, which was revised by all authors. All authors reviewed and agreed with the final version of the report.

Declaration of interests

We declare no competing interests.

Data sharing

Study data are available from the corresponding author on reasonable request.

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together, against malaria transmitted by pyrethroid-resistant mosquitoes: a cluster, randomised controlled, two-by-two factorial design trial. *Lancet* 2018; **391**(10130): 1577-88.

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Vector control for malaria prevention during humanitarian emergencies: a systematic review and meta-analysis

SUPPLEMENTARY APPENDIX

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Supplementary table 1. PRISMA 2020 main checklist and abstract checklist.

PRISMA 2020 Main Checklist

Topic	No.	Item	Location where item is reported
TITLE			
Title	1	Identify the report as a systematic review.	1
ABSTRACT			
Abstract	2	See the PRISMA 2020 for Abstracts checklist	
INTRODUCTION			
Rationale	3	Describe the rationale for the review in the context of existing knowledge.	3
Objectives	4	Provide an explicit statement of the objective(s) or question(s) the review addresses.	6
METHODS			
Eligibility criteria	5	Specify the inclusion and exclusion criteria for the review and how studies were grouped for the syntheses.	6
Information sources	6	Specify all databases, registers, websites, organisations, reference lists and other sources searched or consulted to identify studies. Specify the date when each source was last searched or consulted.	6
Search strategy	7	Present the full search strategies for all databases, registers and websites, including any filters and limits used.	6
Selection process	8	Specify the methods used to decide whether a study met the inclusion criteria of the review, including how many reviewers screened each record and each report retrieved, whether they worked independently, and if applicable, details of automation tools used in the process.	6
Data collection process	9	Specify the methods used to collect data from reports, including how many reviewers collected data from each report, whether they worked independently, any processes for obtaining or confirming data from study investigators, and if applicable, details of automation tools used in the process.	7

Topic	No.	Item	Location where item is reported
Data items	10a	List and define all outcomes for which data were sought. Specify whether all results that were compatible with each outcome domain in each study were sought (e.g. for all measures, time points, analyses), and if not, the methods used to decide which results to collect.	8
	10b	List and define all other variables for which data were sought (e.g. participant and intervention characteristics, funding sources). Describe any assumptions made about any missing or unclear information.	8
Study risk of bias assessment	11	Specify the methods used to assess risk of bias in the included studies, including details of the tool(s) used, how many reviewers assessed each study and whether they worked independently, and if applicable, details of automation tools used in the process.	8
Effect measures	12	Specify for each outcome the effect measure(s) (e.g. risk ratio, mean difference) used in the synthesis or presentation of results.	8
Synthesis methods	13a	Describe the processes used to decide which studies were eligible for each synthesis (e.g. tabulating the study intervention characteristics and comparing against the planned groups for each synthesis (item 5)).	8
	13b	Describe any methods required to prepare the data for presentation or synthesis, such as handling of missing summary statistics, or data conversions.	8
	13c	Describe any methods used to tabulate or visually display results of individual studies and syntheses.	8
	13d	Describe any methods used to synthesize results and provide a rationale for the choice(s). If meta-analysis was performed, describe the model(s), method(s) to identify the presence and extent of statistical heterogeneity, and software package(s) used.	8
	13e	Describe any methods used to explore possible causes of heterogeneity among study results (e.g. subgroup analysis, meta-regression).	8
	13f	Describe any sensitivity analyses conducted to assess robustness of the synthesized results.	8

Topic	No.	Item	Location where item is reported
Reporting bias assessment	14	Describe any methods used to assess risk of bias due to missing results in a synthesis (arising from reporting biases).	8
Certainty assessment	15	Describe any methods used to assess certainty (or confidence) in the body of evidence for an outcome.	8
RESULTS			
Study selection	16a	Describe the results of the search and selection process, from the number of records identified in the search to the number of studies included in the review, ideally using a flow diagram.	10
	16b	Cite studies that might appear to meet the inclusion criteria, but which were excluded, and explain why they were excluded.	Appendix: table 2
Study characteristics	17	Cite each included study and present its characteristics.	Appendix: tables 3 and 4
Risk of bias in studies	18	Present assessments of risk of bias for each included study.	Appendix: tables 7-10
Results of individual studies	19	For all outcomes, present, for each study: (a) summary statistics for each group (where appropriate) and (b) an effect estimate and its precision (e.g. confidence/credible interval), ideally using structured tables or plots.	11-12
Results of syntheses	20a	For each synthesis, briefly summarise the characteristics and risk of bias among contributing studies.	11-23
	20b	Present results of all statistical syntheses conducted. If meta-analysis was done, present for each the summary estimate and its precision (e.g. confidence/credible interval) and measures of statistical heterogeneity. If comparing groups, describe the direction of the effect.	11-23
	20c	Present results of all investigations of possible causes of heterogeneity among study results.	11-23
	20d	Present results of all sensitivity analyses conducted to assess the robustness of the synthesized results.	Appendix: table 5
Reporting biases	21	Present assessments of risk of bias due to missing results (arising from reporting biases) for each synthesis assessed.	Appendix: tables 7-10

Topic	No.	Item	Location where item is reported
Certainty of evidence	22	Present assessments of certainty (or confidence) in the body of evidence for each outcome assessed.	18-23
DISCUSSION			
Discussion	23a	Provide a general interpretation of the results in the context of other evidence.	24-26
	23b	Discuss any limitations of the evidence included in the review.	25-26
	23c	Discuss any limitations of the review processes used.	25-26
	23d	Discuss implications of the results for practice, policy, and future research.	24-26
OTHER INFORMATION			
Registration and protocol	24a	Provide registration information for the review, including register name and registration number, or state that the review was not registered.	9
	24b	Indicate where the review protocol can be accessed, or state that a protocol was not prepared.	7
	24c	Describe and explain any amendments to information provided at registration or in the protocol.	7
Support	25	Describe sources of financial or non-financial support for the review, and the role of the funders or sponsors in the review.	27
Competing interests	26	Declare any competing interests of review authors.	27
Availability of data, code and other materials	27	Report which of the following are publicly available and where they can be found: template data collection forms; data extracted from included studies; data used for all analyses; analytic code; any other materials used in the review.	27

PRIMSA Abstract Checklist

Topic	No.	Item	Reported?
TITLE			

Topic	No.	Item	Reported?
Title	1	Identify the report as a systematic review.	Yes
BACKGROUND			
Objectives	2	Provide an explicit statement of the main objective(s) or question(s) the review addresses.	Yes
METHODS			
Eligibility criteria	3	Specify the inclusion and exclusion criteria for the review.	Yes
Information sources	4	Specify the information sources (e.g. databases, registers) used to identify studies and the date when each was last searched.	Yes
Risk of bias	5	Specify the methods used to assess risk of bias in the included studies.	Yes
Synthesis of results	6	Specify the methods used to present and synthesize results.	Yes
RESULTS			
Included studies	7	Give the total number of included studies and participants and summarise relevant characteristics of studies.	Yes
Synthesis of results	8	Present results for main outcomes, preferably indicating the number of included studies and participants for each. If meta-analysis was done, report the summary estimate and confidence/credible interval. If comparing groups, indicate the direction of the effect (i.e. which group is favoured).	Yes
DISCUSSION			
Limitations of evidence	9	Provide a brief summary of the limitations of the evidence included in the review (e.g. study risk of bias, inconsistency and imprecision).	Yes
Interpretation	10	Provide a general interpretation of the results and important implications.	Yes
OTHER			
Funding	11	Specify the primary source of funding for the review.	Yes
Registration	12	Provide the register name and registration number.	Yes

Supplementary table 2. Characteristics of excluded studies.

Reference	Reason For Exclusion
Abai MR, Raiesi A, Aflatunian M, Jalali M, Kahkha MR, Shahbazi A, Ladonni H, Mahmoodi E, Safari M. Emergency vector control in Bam, Iran. <i>Fifth International Conference on Urban Pests, Singapore 2005</i> ;483.	Conference abstract
Abdi M, Lohrasbi V. Challenges and successes in the prevention and control of infectious diseases after March and April 2019 floods in Iran. <i>Infection Control and Hospital Epidemiology 2020</i> ;41(1):130-131.	Letter to the editor
Abdur Rab M, Freeman TW, Rahim S, Durrani N, Simon-Taha A, Rowland M. High altitude epidemic malaria in Bamian province, central Afghanistan. <i>Eastern Mediterranean Health Journal 2003</i> ;9(3):232-9.	Did not include required exposure (vector control intervention)
Abeyasinghe RR, Galappaththy GN, Smith Gueye C, Kahn JG, Feachem R,G. Malaria control and elimination in Sri Lanka: documenting progress and success factors in a conflict setting. <i>PLoS One 2012</i> ;7(8):e43162.	Review article
Adja AM, Yobo MC, Assi SB. Characterization of malaria transmission during military crisis in urban area of Bouake, Central Cote d'Ivoire. <i>International Journal of Infectious Diseases 2014</i> ;21S:103	Conference abstract
Ahmed B, Nanji K. Preparedness for malaria prevention in relief camps for flood affectees - A cross sectional survey from Pakistan. <i>Journal of Epidemiology and Community Health 2011</i> ;173:S23	Conference abstract
Ahmed B, Nanji K. Preparedness for malaria prevention in relief camps for flood affectees - A cross-sectional survey from Pakistan. <i>Clinical Microbiology and Infection 2011</i> ;17:S210-S211.	Same data used in two articles
Ahmed MO, Daw MA. Mapping the travel route of African refugees who traverse Libya to determine public health implications for Libya and the North-African region. <i>Travel Medicine and Infectious Disease 2016</i> ;14(2):162-4	Letter to the editor
Ajakaye OG, Ibukunoluwa MR. Prevalence and risk of malaria, anemia and malnutrition among children in IDPs camp in Edo State, Nigeria. <i>Parasite Epidemiology and Control 2020</i> ;8:e00127.	Did not include control group/inappropriate study design
Allan R, Nam S, Doull L. MERLIN and malaria epidemic in north-east Kenya. <i>The Lancet 1998</i> ;351(9120):1966-67.	Letter to the editor
Anderson J, Doocy S, Haskew C, Spiegel P, Moss WJ. The burden of malaria in post-emergency refugee sites: A retrospective study. <i>Conflict and Health 2011</i> ;5(1):17.	Unable to link outcome to exposure
Anonymous. Famine-affected, refugee, and displaced populations: recommendations for public health issues. <i>Morbidity and Mortality Weekly Report 1992</i> ;41(RR-13):001.	Did not include required exposure (vector control intervention)
Anonymous. From the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention. Enhanced medical assessment strategy for Barawan Somali refugees--Kenya 1997. <i>JAMA 1998</i> ;279(12):904-5.	Unable to link outcome to exposure
Anonymous. [A third of deaths caused by malaria in Africa are imputable to conflicts and natural disasters]. <i>Sante 2000</i> ;10(5):364-5.	Commentary

Anonymous. Malaria and complex emergencies. <i>Weekly Epidemiological Record</i> 2000;75(27):217.	Commentary
Anonymous. Health fears in wake of tsunami. <i>Expert Review of Anti-Infective Therapy</i> 2005;3:1	Commentary
Anonymous. Early warning, alert and response system in emergencies: a field experience of a novel WHO project in north-east Nigeria. <i>Weekly Epidemiological Record</i> 2017;92(5):45-50.	Did not include required exposure (vector control intervention)
Anonymous. WHO events addressing public health priorities. <i>Eastern Mediterranean Health Journal</i> 2017;23(7):520-21.	Commentary
Arie S. Healthcare for the Rohingya people: Traumatized by violence, trapped in squalor. <i>BMJ</i> 2019;364:k5360.	Commentary
Balaraman K, Sabesan S, Jambulingam P, Gunasekaran K, Boopathi Doss PS. Risk of outbreak of vector-borne diseases in the tsunami hit areas of southern India. <i>The Lancet Infectious Diseases</i> 2005;5(3):128-9.	Commentary
Balasegaram M, Dejene S, Tinnemann P, Perkins S, Davidson R. Examples of tropical disease control in the humanitarian medical programmes of MSF and Merlin. <i>Transactions of the Royal Society of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene</i> 2006;100(4):327-34.	Did not include required exposure (vector control intervention)
Bangs MJ, Subianto DB. El Nino and associated outbreaks of severe malaria in highland populations in Irian Jaya, Indonesia: a review and epidemiological perspective. <i>Southeast Asian Journal of Tropical Medicine and Public Health</i> 1999;30(4):608-19.	Did not include required exposure (vector control intervention)
Bansal RK, Tripathi VS, Desai VK, Singh A. Concerted health efforts prevent and contain diseases after floods disaster in Varachha Zone of Surat. <i>Indian Journal of Community Medicine</i> 2007;32(3):232-33.	Letter to the editor
Baomar A, Mohamed A. Malaria outbreak in a malaria-free region in Oman 1998: unknown impact of civil war in Africa. <i>Public Health</i> 2000;114(6):480-3.	Did not include control group/inappropriate study design
BASF. 100,000 nets for Myanmar [https://agriculture.basf.com/global/en/business-areas/public-health/commitment-to-public-health/mosquito-nets-for-myanmar.html]	Commentary
Basseri HR, Abai MR, Raeisi A, Shahandeh K. Community sleeping pattern and anopheline biting in southeastern Iran: a country earmarked for malaria elimination. <i>American Journal of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene</i> 2012;87(3):499-503.	Did not include required outcome
Basseri HR, Raeisi A, Holakouie K, Shanadeh K. Malaria prevention among Afghani refugees in a malarious area, southeastern Iran. <i>Bulletin de la Societe de Pathologie Exotique</i> 2010;103(5):340-5.	Did not include required outcome
Basseri HR, Holakouie Naieni K, Raeisi A, Shahandeh KH, Ranjbar M, Parvin A. nd M, Ranjbar and A, Parvin[Comparison of knowledge, attitude and practice [KAP] regarding malaria transmission and protection between afghan refugees and Iranian residents in Iranshahr, 2005-2006]. <i>Iranian Journal of Epidemiology</i> 2008;3(3-4):7-13.	Did not include required outcome
Bateman C. Flood disease control--moving smartly to save lives. <i>South African Medical Journal</i> 2000;90(4):330-1.	Commentary
Bayoh MN, Akhwale W, Ombok M, Sang D, Engoki SC, Koros D, Walker ED, Williams HA, Burke H, Armstrong GL, Cetron MS, Weinberg M, Breiman R, Hamel MJ. Malaria in Kakuma refugee camp, Turkana, Kenya: facilitation of <i>Anopheles arabiensis</i> vector populations by installed water distribution and catchment systems. <i>Malaria Journal</i> 2011;10:149.	Did not include control group/inappropriate study design

Borwein S. What do we fear? <i>Hong Kong Practitioner</i> 2005;27(12):447-49.	Commentary
Bouma MJ, Parvez SD, Nesbit R, Sondorp HE. Rapid decomposition of permethrin in the outer fly of an experimental tent in Pakistan. <i>Journal of the American Mosquito Control Association</i> 1996;12(1):125-9.	Did not include required exposure (vector control intervention)
Briet O J, Galappaththy GN, Amerasinghe PH, Konradsen F. Malaria in Sri Lanka: one year post-tsunami. <i>Malaria Journal</i> 2006;5:42.	Did not include control group/inappropriate study design
Briet O J, Galappaththy GN, Konradsen F, Amerasinghe PH, Amerasinghe FP. Maps of the Sri Lanka malaria situation preceding the tsunami and key aspects to be considered in the emergency phase and beyond. <i>Malaria Journal</i> 2005;4:8.	Did not include control group/inappropriate study design
Brooks HM, Paul MKJ, Claude KM, Hawkes M. Malaria in an internally displaced persons camp in the democratic Republic of Congo. <i>American Journal of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene</i> 2016;95:99-100.	Same data used in two articles
Burki T. Infectious diseases in Malian and Syrian conflicts. <i>The Lancet Infectious Diseases</i> 2013;13(4):296-97	Commentary
Campanella N, Tarantini F. Incidence of some infectious diseases in an area of Nicaragua seriously affected by Hurricane Mitch. <i>Igiene Moderna</i> 2000;113:209-23.	Cannot retrieve full text
Carrara VI, Lwin KM, Phyo AP, Ashley E, Wiladphaingern J, Sriprawat K, Rijken M, Boel M, McGready R, Proux S, Chu C, Singhasivanon P, White N, Nosten F. Malaria burden and artemisinin resistance in the mobile and migrant population on the Thai-Myanmar border, 1999-2011: an observational study. <i>PLoS Medicine</i> 2013;10(3):e1001398.	Did not include required exposure (vector control intervention)
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Effect of a Combined Use of Mosquito Repellent and Insecticide Treated Net on Malaria in Ethiopia [https://ClinicalTrials.gov/show/NCT01160809]	Did not include the required study population
Preventing the Spread of Malaria in Mali [https://ClinicalTrials.gov/show/NCT01360112]	Did not include the required study population
Evaluation of Combined Use of ITN's and Insect Repellents Against Malaria [https://ClinicalTrials.gov/show/NCT00144716]	Did not include the required study population
A Stitch in Time May Save Lives: Turning Poor Bednets Into Good Ones [https://ClinicalTrials.gov/show/NCT00169117]	Did not include the required study population
Evaluation of a Novel Long Lasting Insecticidal Net and Indoor Residual Spray Product [https://ClinicalTrials.gov/show/NCT02288637]	Did not include the required study population
Impact of Insecticide-treated Curtains on Antimalarial Drug Resistance [https://ClinicalTrials.gov/show/NCT00169078]	Did not include the required study population
ACT With Chloroquine, Amodiaquine & Sulphadoxine-pyrimethamine in Pakistan [https://clinicaltrials.gov/show/NCT00158548]	Did not include the required study population
Eight Week Primaquine Regimen for the Treatment of Vivax Malaria [https://clinicaltrials.gov/show/NCT00158587]	Did not include the required study population
Insecticide Treated Polyethylene Sheeting for Prevention of Malaria in Emergencies [https://clinicaltrials.gov/show/NCT01456858]	Same data used in two articles

Supplementary table 3. Characteristics of included randomized controlled trials (n=9).

Randomized Controlled Trials											
Study	Country, Site	Study Design	Study Period	Humanitarian Emergency Phase	Humanitarian Emergency Context	Camp/Settlement Structure	Plasmodium Species	Vector Species	Unit of Allocation	Number of Units	Adjustment for Clustering
Smithuis et al. 2013	Myanmar, Dabhine and Myothugyi villages, Rhakine State	cRCT	Nov 1995-Jan 2000	Chronic	Armed conflict between Rohingya Muslim and Rakhine Buddhist communities	Villages around two rural health clinics in Dabhine (Sittwe township) and Myothugyi (Maungdaw township) located 90 km apart	<i>P. falciparum</i> ; <i>P. vivax</i>	ND	Village	20	ICC between children from same community
Rowland et al. 2001	Pakistan, Hangu Valley, North-West Frontier Province	Cross-over RCT [†]	1995-1997	Chronic	Afghan refugees settled in Pakistan fleeing from armed conflict	Villages established 15 years ago; family compounds built from mud/stone in traditional style with animals kept within compound at night	<i>P. falciparum</i> ; <i>P. vivax</i>	<i>An. stephensi</i> ; <i>An. culicifacies</i> ; <i>An. subpictus</i> ; <i>An. fluviatilis</i> ; <i>An. annularis</i>	Refugee settlement	6	ND
Rowland et al. 1999	Pakistan, Adizai refugee settlement, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa Province	Household randomised	Jul-Nov 1996	Chronic	Afghan refugees settled in Pakistan fleeing from armed conflict	Refugee camps established 16 years ago on waterlogged ground near banks of Kabul River; traditional houses built from mud, surrounded by open courtyard and perimeter wall	<i>P. falciparum</i> ; <i>P. vivax</i>	<i>An. stephensi</i> ; <i>An. subpictus</i> ; <i>An. nigerrimus</i>	Household	102	ND
Rowland et al. 1996	Pakistan, Mardan district, North-West Frontier Province	Household randomised	Jul-Dec 1991	Chronic	Afghan refugees settled in Pakistan fleeing from armed conflict	Traditional houses built from mud, surrounded by open courtyard and perimeter wall	<i>P. falciparum</i> ; <i>P. vivax</i>	<i>An. stephensi</i> ; <i>An. culicifacies</i> ; <i>An. subpictus</i> ; <i>An. nigerrimus</i>	Household	359	ND

Rowland et al. 2004	Pakistan, Adizai refugee settlement, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa Province	Household randomised	Aug 1999-Feb 2000	Chronic	Afghan refugees settled in Pakistan fleeing from armed conflict	Traditional houses built from mud, surrounded by open courtyard and perimeter wall	<i>P. falciparum</i> ; <i>P. vivax</i>	<i>An. stephensi</i> ; <i>An. culicifacies</i>	Household	127	ND
Charlwood et al. 2001	Eastern Sudan	cRCT	Sept-Dec 1997	Chronic	Eritrean and Tigrean refugees fleeing armed conflict	Established communities similar to traditional Sudanese villages; inhabitants live in <i>turkels</i> (round walled thatched houses)	<i>P. falciparum</i> ; <i>P. vivax</i>	<i>An. arabiensis</i> ; <i>An. pharoensis</i>	Refugee settlement	14	ND
Dolan et al. 1993	Thai-Burmese Border, Shoklo, Bonoklo and Maesalit villages, 110-130km north of Mae Sod Town	Randomised	Oct 1990-Sept 1992	Chronic	Karen refugees fleeing armed conflict	ND	<i>P. falciparum</i> ; <i>P. vivax</i>	ND	Individual	341	ND
Luxemburger et al. 1994	Thai-Burmese Border, Shoklo village, 110-130km north of Mae Sod Town	Randomised	Aug 1990-Feb 1991	Chronic	Karen refugees fleeing armed conflict	ND	<i>P. falciparum</i> ; <i>P. vivax</i>	ND	Individual	350	ND
McGready et al. 2001	Thailand, western border	Randomised	Apr 1995-Sept 1996	Chronic	Karen refugees fleeing armed conflict	ND	<i>P. falciparum</i> ; <i>P. vivax</i>	ND	Individual	897	ND
Participant Population	Age	Sex	Ethnicity	Method of Recruitment	Vector Control Intervention	Intervention Description/Application Frequency	Intervention Dose/Formulation*	Intervention Coverage	Control	Number of Participants: Intervention	Number of Participants: Control
Households received ITNs; children <10 years old monitored	<10 years	Male and female	Rakhine	Random household selection	ITNs	Assumed to have a useful life of 3 years	Polyester net (11.6m ² or 14.5m ²) with deltamethrin impregnated (25mg/m ²)	Universal coverage (1 ITN per 1.8 people)	No ITNs	3989 (prevalence); 3859 (incidence)	4053 (prevalence); 3969 (incidence)
All community members	All age groups	Male and female	Afghan	Random household selection	Insecticidal livestock treatment	Three rounds of livestock sponging	0.075g/L deltamethrin (K-Othrine	>95% livestock treated (n=5461)	No cattle treatment	37,206 (total community size)	56,329 (total community size)

						(6 weeks between rounds)	2.5%); application rate 30mg/m ²				
All community members	All age groups	Male and female	Afghan	Random household selection	Insecticide treatment of <i>chaddars</i>	Typical <i>chaddar</i> is made from cotton and measures about 3.5m ² ; used as a shield from the sun and for sleeping under	Permethrin (Imperator 25% EC); estimated target dose 1.0g/m ²	10% of camp population (1 <i>chaddar</i> per 1.5 people)	Placebo treatment	765 (prevalence); 15120 (incidence)	845 (prevalence); 15903 (incidence)
All community members	All age groups	Male and female	Afghan	Random household selection	ITNs	Two sizes provided (individual and family sizes)	Polyester nets individually dipped in permethrin (Imperator 25% EC); estimated target dose 0.5g/m ²	ND	No ITNs	1398	1394
All community members	All age groups	Male and female	Afghan	Random household selection	DEET (repellent)	Mosbar repellent soap containing DEET and permethrin; single application gave several hours of protection; one bar lasted an individual several weeks	20% DEET and 0.5% permethrin	ND	Placebo moisturizing lotion with no repellent effect	618	530
All community members	All age groups	Male and female	Eritrean/Tigrean	Random household selection	IRS	Interior walls of all <i>turkels</i> sprayed once; assumed to last 6-8 weeks	2g/m ² malathion	ND	No IRS	134	144
Pregnant women	Women of child-bearing age; mean age=26	Female	Karen	Random allocation	ITNs/UTNs	Participants given ITN or UTN	Nylon net (70x180x150cm) with permethrin impregnated (500mg/m ²) or UTN (100 or 130x180x150cm)	Universal coverage among participants	No study net or women slept under UTN they already owned	103 (ITN); 100 (UTN)	77 (UTN); 27 (no net)

Households received ITNs; children 4-15 years old monitored	4-15 years	Male and female	Karen	Random allocation	ITNs/UTNs	Participants given ITN or UTN	Nets (17.4m ² or 11.9m ²) impregnated with permethrin (Peripel 10); estimated target dose 0.5g/m ²	Universal coverage among participants	UTN	155	163
Pregnant women	Women of child-bearing age; mean age=24	Female	Karen	ND	Repellent	Popular local cosmetic repellent applied to arms and leg every evening at 17:00; daily compliance monitored	Thanaka + 20% DET	Universal coverage among participants	Thanaka	449	448

Outcome Measurements

Factors Adjusted For	Epidemiological					Entomological			Operational	Adverse Events	Unintended Effects
	MI*	PR	MT	SM	AN	EIR	DN	SR	DB		
ND	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No	No	No	No	No
ND	Yes	Yes	No	No	No	No	Yes	No	No	Yes	Yes
Intra-household clustering	Yes	Yes	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	Yes	No
ND	Yes	Yes	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No
ND	No	Yes	No	No	No	No	Yes	No	No	Yes	No
Village; month	Yes	No	Yes	No	No	No	Yes	Yes	No	No	No
Parity/gravid ae	Yes	Yes	No	No	Yes	No	No	No	No	Yes	No
ND	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No	No	No	No	Yes	Yes	No
ND	No	Yes	No	No	Yes	No	No	No	No	No	No

AN: anaemia prevalence; cRCT: cluster-randomized controlled trials; DB: intervention durability; DN: adult mosquito density; EC: emulsifiable concentrate; EIR: entomological inoculation rate; ICC: intra-cluster correlation; IRS: indoor residual spraying; ITN: insecticide-treated net; MI: malaria incidence; MT: all-cause mortality; ND: not described; PR: malaria prevalence; SM: severe malaria; SR: sporozoite rate; UTN: untreated net.

*Cross-over RCT; one group of 3 villages treated in year 1 and 3, the other group treated in year 2.

#For insecticidal interventions.

*Case incidence and/or infection incidence

Supplementary table 4. Characteristics of included non-randomized controlled studies (n=15).

Non-Randomized Controlled Studies											
Study	Country, Site	Study Design	Study Period	Humanitarian Emergency Phase	Humanitarian Emergency Context	Camp/Settlement Structure	<i>Plasmodium</i> Species	Vector Species	Unit of Allocation /Survey	Number of Units	Participant Population
Rowland et al. 2002	Afghanistan, Behsud and Chaprahar, Nangarhar Province	Cross-sectional and case-control	Apr 1995-Nov 1996	Chronic	Afghan refugees resettled in Afghanistan (from Pakistan)	Villages in Nangarhar were destroyed by fighting during the war in 1995, many inhabitants had returned from refugee camps in Pakistan and rebuilt their homes and repaired their environment (de-mining and irrigation systems)	<i>P. falciparum</i> ; <i>P. vivax</i>	<i>An. stephensi</i> ; <i>An. fluviatilis</i> ; <i>An. culicifacies</i> ; <i>An. pulcherrimus</i>	Village	12	All community members
Brooks et al. 2017a	Democratic Republic of the Congo, Birambizo refugee settlement, Walikale district, North Kivu Province	Cross-sectional	Apr 2015-Mar 2017	Chronic	Local population fleeing from armed conflict	Shelters made of tarpaulin walls and roof, with a mud/dirt floor	<i>P. falciparum</i>	ND	Refugee settlement	1	All community members
Brooks et al. 2017b	Democratic Republic of the Congo, Lushebere refugee settlement, Masisi region	Cross-sectional	Jan-Jul 2014	Chronic	Local population fleeing from armed conflict	Lushebere is the largest IDP camp in the region formed in 2013 when approximately 1100 IDPs arrived, followed by a second wave of 1500 in 2014	<i>P. falciparum</i>	ND	Refugee settlement	1	All community members
Charchuk et al. 2016	Democratic Republic of the Congo, Bilobilo camp, near Mubi village, Walikale District, North Kivu Province	Cross-sectional and case-control	Jan-Jul 2013	Chronic	Local population fleeing from armed conflict	Temporary housing structures build from tarpaulin and thatch, covering an area of 1km ²	<i>P. falciparum</i>	ND	Refugee settlement	2	All community members

Ma et al. 2017	Democratic Republic of the Congo, Butembo, Beni and Goma, North Kivu Province	Cross-sectional	Aug-Oct 2012	Chronic	Local population fleeing from armed conflict	Study conducted in three semi-urban cities; estimated populations were Butembo: 600,000, Beni: 200,000, Goma: 1 million	<i>P. falciparum</i>	ND	Semi-urban city	3	Households received ITNs; aged 2 months to 5 years monitored
Kimani et al. 2006	Kenya, Dadaab refugee settlement, Garissa District, North Eastern Province	Non-randomized	Apr-Aug 2002	Chronic	Somalian refugees fleeing from armed conflict	Study conducted in three sub refugee camps (Ifo, Hagadera and Dagahaley) with an estimated total population of 130,000 people; sub-camps were divided into blocks consisting of 600-700 people with several households living under one roof	ND	ND	Refugee settlement	3	All community members
Bouma et al. 1996	Pakistan, South Waziristan Agency	Before-after	1989-1991	Chronic	Afghan refugees settled in Pakistan fleeing from armed conflict	Estimated 30,000 Afghan refugees living among Pakistani Pathans with a further 25,000-30,000 semi-nomadic Afghan refugees in the area between May-Sep. Most refugees use fly-sheeted, ridge-pole tents (4x2.1x3.5m) provided by UNHCR	<i>P. falciparum</i> ; <i>P. vivax</i>	<i>An. stephensi</i> ; <i>An. culicifacies</i>	ND	ND	All community members
Rowland et al. 1994	Pakistan, M. Khoja, Darsamund, Y. Ghund, Baghicha, Doaba, Jalala, Gandaf, Azakhel, Kahi, Badaber, Dallan, Kotki, Kagan, Adizai,	Controlled before-after	Jun-Nov 1993	Chronic	Afghan refugees settled in Pakistan fleeing from armed conflict	Refugee villages situated on marginal land with houses made from mud, separated by purdah walls	<i>P. falciparum</i> ; <i>P. vivax</i>	<i>An. stephensi</i> ; <i>An. culicifacies</i> ; <i>An. subpictus</i> ; <i>An. superpictus</i> ; <i>An. annularis</i> ;	Village	14	School children

	North-West Frontier Province							<i>An. fluviatilis</i>			
Rowland et al. 1997a	Pakistan, Baghicha and Kagan, Mardan District, North-West Frontier Province	Cross-sectional	1991-1994	Chronic	Afghan refugees settled in Pakistan fleeing from armed conflict	Extended family groups of Afghan refugees live in houses constructed from mud, located within high-walled compounds; community members sleep outside during the summer	<i>P. falciparum</i> ; <i>P. vivax</i>	ND	Household	359	All community members
Rowland et al. 1997b	Pakistan, Behsud and Chaprahar, Nangarhar province	Before-after	1993-1994	Chronic	Afghan refugees settled in Pakistan fleeing from armed conflict	ND	<i>P. falciparum</i> ; <i>P. vivax</i>	<i>An. maculatus</i> ; <i>An. pulcherrimus</i> ; ; <i>An. nigerrimus</i> ; <i>An. stephensi</i> ; <i>An. culicifacies</i> ; <i>An. subpictus</i> ; <i>An. superpictus</i> ; <i>An. annularis</i> ; <i>An. fluviatilis</i>	Village	14	All community members
Wahid et al. 2016	Pakistan, Mardan (Baghecha, Kaghan and Jalala camps) and Peshawar (Adezai) districts in Khyber Pakhunkwa Province and Zangal Patai camp in the Malakand	Cross-sectional	Jun-Sept 2010	Chronic	Afghan refugees settled in Pakistan fleeing from armed conflict	Houses primarily constructed with rocks, bricks and mud; free primary health care provided at basic health units in each camp and run by UNHCR	<i>P. falciparum</i> ; <i>P. vivax</i>	<i>An. stephensi</i> ; <i>An. culicifacies</i>	Refugee camp	5	All community members

	agency tribal area										
Burns et al. 2012	Sierra Leone, Largo and Tobanda camps, Kenema District	Cohort	Dec 2003-Jul 2004	Chronic	Local population fleeing from armed conflict	Study design attempted to simulate the acute phase of an emergency; rudimentary shelters constructed from polyethylene sheeting (Largo), compared to a chronic emergency (Tobanda), where families construct mud walled huts	<i>P. falciparum</i>	<i>An. gambiae</i> s.l.; <i>An. funestus</i> s.l.	Refugee camp sub-sections	4	Families received ITPS; aged 4-36 months monitored
Eshag et al. 2020	Sudan, Ardamata camp, Al-Geneina City	Cross-sectional	Jul-Dec 2018	Chronic	Local population fleeing from armed conflict	ND	<i>P. falciparum</i> ; <i>P. vivax</i>	ND	Refugee camp	1	All community members
Spencer et al. 2004	Uganda, Bundibugyo (urban) and Nyahuka (rural) camps	Cross-sectional	Jun 2001-Jul 2002	Chronic	Local population fleeing from armed conflict	Camps organized as small windowless mud houses with roofs of tin or plastic sheeting	<i>P. falciparum</i>	ND	Refugee camp	22	All community members
Chan et al. 2017	Vanuatu, Islands of Tanna, Aneityum and Erromango, Tafea Province	Cross-sectional	Jun-Jul 2015	Acute	On 13th March 2015, Tropical Cyclone Pam struck Vanuatu. Tafea Province was directly in the path and was one of the worst hit areas	Aneityum had small, concentrated population in 3 communities; Erromango and Tanna had larger, more dispersed populations	<i>P. falciparum</i> ; <i>P. vivax</i>	ND	Community	12	All community members
Age	Sex	Ethnicity	Method of Recruitment	Vector Control Intervention Exposure	Intervention Description/Application Frequency	Intervention Dose/Formulation[#]	Intervention Coverage	Control	Number of Participants: Exposure	Number of Participants: Control	Factors Adjusted For
All age groups	Male and female	Afghans	Random selection	ITNs + UTNs	Participants given ITN or UTN; 3/6 villages in each district received nets in year 1,	Polyester net treated with either permethrin (500mg/m ²) or lambda-cyhalothrin (25mg/m ²)	56% of families bought nets in year 1; 54% in year 2	No ITN	2319	1343	Age; sex; district; study period

					while the other 3 received nets in year 2						
All age groups	Male and female	Congolese	Random selection	ITNs	ND	ND	29% of households owned a bed net (median 3 people per ITN); no households owned more than one net	No ITN	85	326	ND
All age groups	Male and female	Congolese	Febrile patients presenting for treatment at health centre	ITNs	ND	ND	60% (452/751) of febrile patients lived in households with ITNs; of these 59% (269/452) reported sleeping under the net	No ITN	269	1020	Age; sex; ITN ownership; duration lived in camp; literacy
Children under 5 years	Male and female	Congolese/Nande	Random selection (cross-sectional); febrile patients presenting for treatment at health centre (case-control)	ITNs	ND	ND	Cross-sectional: in the camp, 34% lived in a household with an ITN, 25% slept under ITN. In the village, 68% lived in a household with an ITN, 56% slept under ITN. Case-control: in	No ITN	200 cross-sectional; 100 case-control	200 cross-sectional; 100 case-control	ND

							the camp, 21% lived in a household with an ITN, 16% slept under ITN. In the village 75% lived in a house with an ITN, 65% slept under ITN				
Children aged 2 months to 5 years	Male and female	Congolese/Nande	Children presenting to the well-child and/or immunization clinics	ITNs	ND	ND	38% (245/643) of participants reported owning an ITN, and 26% (169/643) of children slept under the ITN the previous night	No ITN	169	473	Age; study site
All age groups	Male and female	Somalian	Random selection	ITCs	<i>Diras, galbasaar (saris)</i> and <i>jalbaabs</i> treated every 3 weeks (approx. every 5 washes)	Clothing dipped in permethrin (Peripel EC 55; 0.00375%)	100% coverage in participating households	UTC (dipped in water)	198	101	ITN use; age; sex; sleeping location; use of other malaria control tools
All age groups	Male and female	Afghan; Pakistani	Random selection	Insecticide treatment of tents	Tents sprayed once during 1990	Tents consisted of a cotton canvas outer flysheet (480g/m ²) and an inner compartment made from two identical cotton sheets (390g/m ² combined); inner surface area (30m ²) sprayed with 25% EC permethrin (Imperator	95.5% of tents sprayed	IRS (malathion; 50% water soluble powder at 2g/m ²) on house walls	27300	98000	Age

						ICI); estimated target dose of 0.5g/m ²					
School children aged 5-15 years	Male and female	Afghan	All eligible children	IRS	Malathion or lambda-cyhalothrin sprayed over a 6-week period	Malathion estimated target dose of 2.04g/m ² (50% WP; Cyanamid); lambda-cyhalothrin estimated target dose 26mg/m ² (10% WP; Icon)	95% coverage in malathion villages; 97% in lambda-cyhalothrin villages	No IRS	2600	221	Age
All age groups	Male and female	Afghan	Random selection	ITNs	Families issued with mainly double-sized nets; some single-sizes as well	Polyester 100-denier nets dipped in aqueous solution of permethrin (25% EC Imperator); estimated target dose of 0.5g/m ²	Average number of nets issues was sufficient for a family of 8.6 persons (average family size=7.8)	No ITN	173	186	ND
All age groups	Male and female	Afghan	Passive case detection	IRS	8 villages randomly selected for spraying in April; 6 villages for spraying in July	5 villages sprayed with lambda-cyhalothrin (30mg/m ² ; Icon; 10% WP) and 9 villages sprayed with malathion (2g/m ² ; Cheminova; 50% WP)	97% of 23,708 houses sprayed	No IRS	2683	225	Age
All age groups	Male and female	Afghan	Random selection	ITNs + IRS	ND	ND	Reported ITN use ranged from 3.2-63.7%; IRS in the previous 12 months was (≤10.0 %)	No ITN or IRS	695	110	Age; camp residency; fever in the last 2 weeks; ITN use; repellent use
Children aged 4-36 months	Male and female	Liberian	All houses eligible for intervention/control ; random selection of children for monitoring	ITPS	Largo: all interior walls/roof lined with ITPS/UPS, blocking eaves. Tobanda: only roof/ceiling	Deltamethrin (ITPS pre-treated by manufacturer, formulation not specified)	Full coverage with either ITPS or UPS	UPS	106	116	Age; gender

All age groups	Male and female	Sudanese	Passive case detection	ITNs	covered with ITPS/UPS ND	ND	97.9% (372/380) owned an ITN	No ITN	372	8	ND
All age groups	Male and female	Ugandan	Random selection	ITNs	Each household received 1-4 ITNs depending on number of inhabitants	PermaNet ITNs	25,552 ITNs distributed to 16,687 houses containing 67,712 people in 22 camps	No ITN	1169	ND	ND
All age groups	Male and female	Melanesian/Polynesian	ND	ITNs	ND	ND	Reported ITN use was 72.8%	No ITN	3009	ND	ND

Outcome Measurements

Epidemiological					Entomological			Operational	Adverse Events	Unintended Effects	Inclusion In Meta-Analysis
MI*	PR*	MT	SM	AN	EIR	DN	SR	DB			
No	Yes	No	No	No	No	Yes	No	No	No	No	Yes
No	Yes	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	Yes
No	Yes	No	Yes	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	Yes
No	Yes	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	Yes
No	Yes	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	Yes
No	Yes	No	No	No	No	Yes	No	No	No	Yes	Yes
No	Yes	No	No	No	No	No	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	No
No	Yes	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	Yes
No	Yes	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	Yes
No	Yes	No	No	No	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No	Yes
No	Yes	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	Yes
Yes	Yes	No	No	Yes	No	No	No	No	Yes	No	Yes
No	Yes	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	Yes
No	Yes	No	No	Yes	No	No	No	Yes	No	No	Yes
No	Yes	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No

AN: anaemia prevalence; DB: intervention durability; DN: adult mosquito density; EIR: entomological inoculation rate; IDP: internally-displaced person; IRS: indoor residual spraying; ITC: insecticide-treated clothing; ITN: insecticide-treated net; ITPS: insecticide-treated plastic sheeting; MI: malaria incidence; MT: all-cause mortality; NA: not applicable; ND: not described; PR: malaria prevalence; SM: severe malaria; SR: sporozoite rate; UNHCR: United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees; UPS: untreated plastic sheeting; UTC: untreated clothing; UTN: untreated net; WP: wettable powder.

#For insecticidal interventions.

*Case incidence and/or infection incidence

^Case prevalence and/or parasite prevalence

Supplementary table 5. Data analyses: randomized controlled trials (n=9).

Comparison 1. ITNs vs no ITNs

Outcome or subgroup	No. of studies	No. of participants	Statistical method	Effect size
1.1 <i>P. falciparum</i> case incidence	4	3200	Risk ratio (M-H, Random, 95% CI)	0.55 [0.37, 0.79]
1.2 <i>P. vivax</i> case incidence	3	2997	Risk ratio (M-H, Random, 95% CI)	0.69 [0.51, 0.94]
1.3 <i>P. falciparum</i> prevalence	2	2097	Risk ratio (M-H, Random, 95% CI)	0.60 [0.40, 0.88]
1.4 <i>P. vivax</i> prevalence	2	2097	Risk ratio (M-H, Random, 95% CI)	1.00 [0.75, 1.34]
1.5 Anaemia prevalence (<10g/dL)	1	357	Risk ratio (M-H, Random, 95% CI)	0.95 [0.81, 1.11]

Comparison 2. IRS vs no IRS

Outcome or subgroup	No. of studies	No. of participants	Statistical method	Effect size
2.1 <i>P. falciparum</i> parasite prevalence (unadjusted)	1	48715	Risk ratio (M-H, Fixed, 95% CI)	1.30 [1.26, 1.33]
2.2 <i>P. falciparum</i> parasite prevalence (adjusted, ICC=0.05)	1	278	Risk ratio (M-H, Random, 95% CI)	1.31 [0.91, 1.88]
2.3 <i>P. falciparum</i> parasite prevalence (sensitivity ICC=0.01)	1	1361	Risk ratio (M-H, Random, 95% CI)	1.30 [1.10, 1.53]
2.4 <i>P. falciparum</i> parasite prevalence (sensitivity ICC=0.1)	1	139	Risk ratio (M-H, Random, 95% CI)	1.24 [0.74, 2.08]

Comparison 3. Topical repellent vs no topical repellent

Outcome or subgroup	No. of studies	No. of participants	Statistical method	Effect size
3.1 <i>P. falciparum</i>	2	1822	Risk ratio (M-H, Random, 95% CI)	0.58 [0.35, 0.97]
3.2 <i>P. vivax</i>	2	1822	Risk ratio (M-H, Random, 95% CI)	1.06 [0.60, 1.85]
3.3 Anaemia	1	587	Risk ratio (M-H, Fixed, 95% CI)	1.06 [0.91, 1.23]

Comparison 4. Insecticide-treated *chaddars* and top-sheets vs no insecticide-treated *chaddars* and top-sheets

Outcome or subgroup	No. of studies	No. of participants	Statistical method	Effect size
5.1 <i>P. falciparum</i> case incidence	1	825	Risk ratio (M-H, Random, 95% CI)	0.56 [0.41, 0.78]
5.2 <i>P. vivax</i> case incidence	1	825	Risk ratio (M-H, Random, 95% CI)	0.74 [0.54, 1.02]
5.3 <i>P. falciparum</i> case incidence (adjusted, ICC=0.03)	1	682	Risk ratio (M-H, Random, 95% CI)	0.56 [0.39, 0.80]
5.4 <i>P. vivax</i> case incidence (adjusted, ICC=0.03)	1	682	Risk ratio (M-H, Random, 95% CI)	0.59 [0.42, 0.82]
5.5 <i>P. falciparum</i> case incidence (sensitivity analysis, ICC=0.01)	1	771	Risk ratio (M-H, Random, 95% CI)	0.57 [0.41, 0.79]
5.6 <i>P. falciparum</i> case incidence (sensitivity analysis, ICC=0.05)	1	771	Risk ratio (M-H, Random, 95% CI)	0.59 [0.43, 0.81]

5.7 <i>P. falciparum</i> case incidence (sensitivity analysis, ICC=0.05)	1	611	Risk ratio (M-H, Random, 95% CI)	0.57 [0.39, 0.83]
5.8 <i>P. vivax</i> case incidence (sensitivity analysis, ICC=0.05)	1	611	Risk ratio (M-H, Random, 95% CI)	0.58 [0.41, 0.83]

Supplementary table 6. Data analyses: non-randomized studies (n=14).

Comparison 1. ITNs vs no ITNs

Outcome or subgroup	No. of studies	No. of participants	Statistical method	Effect size
1.1 <i>P. falciparum</i> prevalence: cross-sectional studies (crude ORs)	7	12347	Odds Ratio (M-H, Random, 95% CI)	0.56 [0.40, 0.77]
1.2 <i>P. falciparum</i> prevalence: cross-sectional studies (adjusted ORs)	2	7413	Odds Ratio (IV, Random, 95% CI)	0.64 [0.46, 0.89]
1.3 <i>P. vivax</i> prevalence: cross-sectional studies (crude ORs)	3	9921	Odds Ratio (M-H, Random, 95% CI)	0.80 [0.62, 1.03]
1.4 <i>P. vivax</i> prevalence: cross-sectional studies (adjusted ORs)	1	6771	Odds Ratio (IV, Random, 95% CI)	0.61 [0.33, 1.12]
1.5 <i>P. falciparum</i> case prevalence: cross-sectional and case-control studies (crude ORs)	4	42534	Odds Ratio (M-H, Random, 95% CI)	0.22 [0.12, 0.39]

1.6 <i>P. falciparum</i> case prevalence: cross-sectional and case-control studies (adjusted ORs)	3	36465	Odds Ratio (IV, Fixed, 95% CI)	0.26 [0.21, 0.31]
1.7 <i>P. vivax</i> case prevalence: cross-sectional and case-control studies (crude ORs)	2	43479	Odds Ratio (M-H, Random, 95% CI)	0.73 [0.67, 0.80]
1.8 <i>P. vivax</i> case prevalence: cross-sectional and case-control studies (adjusted ORs)	1	35514	Odds Ratio (IV, Fixed, 95% CI)	0.87 [0.82, 0.94]
1.9 Anaemia: cross-sectional studies (crude ORs)	1	1169	Mean Difference (IV, Fixed, 95% CI)	-0.10 [-0.34, 0.14]

Comparison 2. IRS vs no IRS

Outcome or subgroup	No. of studies	No. of participants	Statistical method	Effect size
2.1 <i>P. falciparum</i> prevalence: cross-sectional, case-control and cohort studies (crude ORs)	2	4708	Odds Ratio (M-H, Random, 95% CI)	0.18 [0.01, 5.59]
2.2 <i>P. vivax</i> prevalence: cross-sectional, case-control and cohort studies (crude ORs)	2	4708	Odds Ratio (M-H, Random, 95% CI)	0.74 [0.25, 2.15]
2.3 <i>P. falciparum</i> malaria incidence: before-after studies (crude ORs)	1	480372	Odds Ratio (M-H, Fixed, 95% CI)	0.57 [0.53, 0.61]

2.4 <i>P. vivax</i> malaria incidence: before-after studies (crude ORs)	1	480372	Odds Ratio (M-H, Fixed, 95% CI)	0.51 [0.49, 0.52]
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Comparison 3. Insecticide-treated plastic sheeting vs no insecticide-treated plastic sheeting

Outcome or subgroup	No. of studies	No. of participants	Statistical method	Effect size
3.1 <i>P. falciparum</i> parasite prevalence: cohort studies (crude ORs)	1	1610	Odds Ratio (M-H, Fixed, 95% CI)	0.87 [0.72, 1.06]
3.2 <i>P. falciparum</i> parasite prevalence: cohort studies (adjusted ORs)	1	1556	Odds Ratio (IV, Fixed, 95% CI)	0.80 [0.64, 1.00]
3.3 <i>P. falciparum</i> malaria incidence: cohort studies (crude IRRs)	1	222	Risk Ratio (IV, Fixed, 95% CI)	0.65 [0.63, 0.68]
3.4 <i>P. falciparum</i> malaria incidence: cohort studies (adjusted IRRs)	1	222	Odds Ratio (IV, Fixed, 95% CI)	0.68 [0.62, 0.74]
3.5 Anaemia: cohort studies (crude ORs)	1	436	Mean Difference (IV, Fixed, 95% CI)	0.71 [0.48, 0.94]
3.6 <i>P. falciparum</i> prevalence: before-after studies (crude ORs)	1	102	Odds Ratio (IV, Fixed, 95% CI)	0.28 [0.11, 0.69]

Comparison 4. ITNs + IRS vs no ITNs + IRS

Outcome or subgroup	No. of studies	No. of participants	Statistical method	Effect size
4.1 <i>P. vivax</i> parasite prevalence: cross-sectional studies (crude ORs)	1	805	Odds Ratio (M-H, Random, 95% CI)	0.26 [0.10, 0.67]

Comparison 5. Insecticide-treated clothing vs no insecticide-treated clothing

Outcome or subgroup	No. of studies	No. of participants	Statistical method	Effect size
5.1 <i>P. falciparum</i> parasite prevalence: cross-sectional studies (crude ORs)	1	181	Odds Ratio (M-H, Fixed, 95% CI)	0.31 [0.17, 0.58]
5.2 <i>P. falciparum</i> parasite prevalence: cross-sectional studies (adjusted ORs)	1	181	Odds Ratio (IV, Fixed, 95% CI)	0.29 [0.14, 0.60]

Comparison 6. Insecticide-treated clothing vs no insecticide-treated clothing

Outcome or subgroup	No. of studies	No. of participants	Statistical method	Effect size
6.1 <i>P. falciparum</i> parasite prevalence: cross-sectional studies (crude ORs)	1	2797	Odds Ratio (M-H, Random, 95% CI)	0.38 [0.20, 0.70]
6.2 <i>P. vivax</i> parasite prevalence: cross-sectional	1	2842	Odds Ratio (M-H, Random, 95% CI)	1.89 [1.27, 2.82]

studies (crude ORs)				
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Supplementary table 7. Risk of bias summary: randomized controlled trials (n=9).

Study	Risk of bias domains						Overall
	D1	D1b	D2	D3	D4	D5	
Smithius 2013	+	+	+	+	+	-	-
Dolan 1993	+	+	+	+	+	-	-
Luxemburger 1994	+	+	+	+	+	-	-
Rowland 1996	+	+	+	+	+	-	-
Rowland 1999	+	+	+	-	+	-	-
Rowland 2001	+	+	+	+	+	-	-
Rowland 2004	+	+	+	+	+	-	-
McGready 2001	+	+	+	+	+	-	-
Charlwood 2001	+	+	+	+	+	-	-

Domains:
D1 : Bias arising from the randomization process.
D1b: Bias arising from the timing of identification and recruitment of Individual participants in relation to timing of randomization.
D2 : Bias due to deviations from intended intervention.
D3 : Bias due to missing outcome data.
D4 : Bias in measurement of the outcome.
D5 : Bias in selection of the reported result.

Judgement
- Some concerns
+ Low

Supplementary table 8. Risk of bias summary: case-control studies (n=2).

Reference	Selection				Comparability	Exposure			Overall quality assessment score (max 9)
	Is the case definition adequate?	Representativeness of the cases	Selection of controls	Definition of controls	Comparability of cases and controls on the basis of the design or analysis	Ascertainment of exposure	Same method of ascertainment for cases and controls	Non-response rate	
*	a) Yes, with independent validation	a) Consecutive or obviously representative series of cases	a) Community controls	a) No history of disease (endpoint)	a) Study controls for age	a) Secure record (e.g. Surgical records)	a) Yes	a) Same rate for both groups	
					b) Study controls for gender, house/shelter construction, duration in camp or socioeconomic status	b) Structured interview where blind to case/control status			
	b) Yes, e.g. record linkage or based on self-reports	b) Potential for selection biases or not stated	b) Hospital controls	b) No description of source	c) No description	c) Interview not blinded to case/control status	b) No	b) Non-respondents described	
						d) Written self-report or medical record only		c) Rate different and no designation or no description	
c) No description		c) No description	c) Other		e) No description				
Charchuk 2016	a)*	b)	b)	c)	c)	c)	a)*	c)	2
Rowland 2002	a)*	b)	b)	b)	a)* and b)*	c)	a)*	c)	3

Supplementary table 9. Risk of bias summary: cross-sectional studies (n=11).

Study	Selection				Comparability	Outcome		Overall quality assessment (max = 10)	
	Representativeness of the sample	Sample size	Non-respondents	Ascertainment of exposure (risk factor)	Comparability of groups on basis of the design or analysis	Ascertainment of outcome	Statistical test		
	**			a) Validated measurement tool		a) Validated measurement tool			
	*	a) Truly representative of the average individual or household in the community b) Somewhat representative of the average individual or household in the community	a) Justified and satisfactory (power calculation included)	a) Comparability between respondents and non-respondents characteristics is established, and the response rate is satisfactory	b) Non-validated measurement tool, but the tool is available or described	a) Study controls for age b) Study controls for gender, house/shelter construction, duration in camp or socioeconomic status	b) Non-validated measurement method, but the method is available or described	a) The statistical test used to analyse the data is clearly described and appropriate, and the measurement of the association is presented, including confidence intervals and probability level	
		c) Selected group of users e.g. nurses, volunteers d) No description of the derivation of the sample	b) Not justified	b) The response rate is unsatisfactory, or the comparability between respondents and non-respondents is unsatisfactory c) No description of response rate or the characteristics or the responders and non-responders	c) No description of the measurement tool	c) Study does not control for other factors	c) No description of the measurement tool	b) The statistical test is not appropriate, not described or incomplete	
Brooks 2017a	a)*	b)	c)	c)	a)* and b)*	a)**	a)*	6	
Brooks 2017b	a)*	a)*	c)	b)*	c)	a)**	a)*	6	
Charchuk 2016	b)*	a)*	c)	b)*	c)	a)**	a)*	6	
Eshag 2020	c)	a)*	c)	b)*	c)	a)**	a)*	5	
Kimani 2006	a)*	b)	c)	b)*	a)* and b)*	a)**	a)*	7	
Ma 2017	c)	a)*	c)	b)*	a)* and b)*	a)**	a)*	7	
Rowland 1994	b)*	b)	c)	b)*	a)*	a)**	b)	5	
Rowland 1997	a)*	b)	c)	b)*	c)	a)**	a)*	5	
Rowland 2002	a)*	b)	c)	b)*	a)* and b)*	a)**	a)*	7	
Spencer 2004	a)*	a)*	c)	b)*	c)	a)**	a)*	6	
Wahid 2016	a)*	a)*	c)	b)*	a)* and b)*	a)**	a)*	8	

Supplementary table 10. Risk of bias summary: cohort study (n=1).

	Selection				Comparability	Outcome			Overall quality assessment (max = 9)
	Representativeness of the exposed cohort	Selection of the non-exposed cohort	Ascertainment of exposure (risk factor)	Demonstration that outcome of interest was not present at start of study	Comparability of groups on basis of the design or analysis	Ascertainment of outcome	Was follow-up long enough for outcomes to occur?	Adequacy of follow-up of cohorts	
Study	a) Truly representative of the average individual or household in the community	a) Drawn from the same community as the exposed cohort	a) Secure record (e.g. surgical records)	a) Yes	a) Study controls for age	a) Independent blind assessment	a) Yes	a) Complete follow up – all subjects accounted for	
	b) Somewhat representative of the average individual or household in the community		b) Structured interview		b) Study controls for gender, house/shelter construction, duration in camp or socioeconomic status	b) Record linkage		b) Subjects lost to follow up unlikely to introduce bias	
	c) Selected group of users e.g. nurses, volunteers	b) Drawn from a different source	c) Written self-report	b) No	c) Study does not control for other factors	c) Self report	b) No	c) Follow-up rate <20% and no description of those lost	
	d) No description of the derivation of the cohort	c) No description of the derivation of the non-exposed cohort	d) No description			d) No description		d) No statement	
Burns 2012	a)*	a)*	a)*	b)	a)* and b)*	a)*	a)*	b)*	8